

BOOK *of* ABSTRACTS

2024

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Book of Abstracts

Institute of Marine Biology
University of Montenegro
Kotor, Montenegro
2024

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THE CONFERENCE

Welcome to the Third International Conference: Adriatic Biodiversity Protection – AdriBioPro2024. This landmark event, commemorating the 50th anniversary of the University of Montenegro and 25 years of the AdriaMed project, promises to be a pivotal gathering for advancing marine science and policy in the South Adriatic region. Against the dynamic backdrop of the SKILLS initiative, AdriBioPro2024 is dedicated to addressing the critical challenges and opportunities within the blue economy.

Participants

Our conference brings together a diverse community of researchers, policymakers, stakeholders, and enthusiasts, all united in their commitment to marine biodiversity, conservation, and sustainable practices. Through a series of plenary sessions, breakout discussions, and the engaging South Adriatic Sea Food Fair, participants will explore pressing issues such as marine litter, aquaculture, climate change impacts, and the conservation of aquatic ecosystems.

Format

Building on the successful formats of previous conferences, AdriBioPro2024 will foster a vibrant platform for sharing state-of-the-art research and innovative solutions. The insights gained here will be instrumental in shaping future marine science priorities and policies, ensuring a resilient and vibrant Adriatic environment. As we strive to balance conservation efforts with the development of the blue economy, this conference marks a significant step forward in our collective journey toward sustainable maritime heritage.

Background

University of Montenegro

In 2024, the University of Montenegro celebrates five decades of continuous contribution to Montenegrin society. The University of Montenegro has been and remains a field of challenging struggle for knowledge, freedom, and progress, where battles for the future of the country are fought through education, science, and art. Over the past fifty years, the university has played a pivotal role in nurturing the intellectual and cultural fabric of Montenegro, providing a platform for innovation and critical thinking that propels the nation forward.

AdriaMed Project

The FAO-AdriaMed Project (Scientific Cooperation to Support Responsible Fisheries in the Adriatic Sea) is an FAO Regional Project funded by the Italian Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry Policies (MiPAAF), the European Commission since 2007, and the Croatian Ministry of Agriculture since January

2016. Operative since September 1999, the project aims to promote scientific cooperation among Adriatic countries, including Albania, Croatia, Italy, Montenegro, and Slovenia. By aligning with the Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries (FAO 1995), AdriaMed seeks to enhance the management of fishing activities, contributing to a broader understanding of the Adriatic Sea's shared fishery resources. This initiative is crucial for the sustainable management of biological resources that transcend geopolitical boundaries.

SKILLS Project

The SKILLS project, spanning from September 2023 to December 2027, aims to bolster the availability of skilled labor in the South Adriatic region's blue economy sectors. With a total budget of close to 6 million euros, including significant EU funding of 4 million euros, the project operates through a consortium of diverse partners. These include the University of Montenegro - Institute of Marine Biology as the lead partner, the Department of Labor Market Policies, Education, Training from Puglia Region, Italy, the Service for the Competitiveness of Productive Systems from Molise Region, Italy, the State Agency for Strategic Programming and Aid Coordination, Albania, the Ministry of Economic Development of Montenegro, and the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Albania. Through collaborative efforts, the SKILLS project endeavors to enhance existing educational pathways, establish novel ones, and implement on-the-job training schemes, thereby empowering the workforce and fostering economic growth in the region.

Content

AdriBioPro2024 is more than a conference; it is a call to action for the protection and sustainable use of our marine resources. Let us embark on this journey of exploration, collaboration, and innovation, working together to ensure a prosperous and sustainable future for the South Adriatic region.

Topics Addressed

1. Marine and freshwater biodiversity, systematics, taxonomy, and data management
2. Climate change and impacts to marine ecosystem
3. Aquatic alien and invasive species
4. Fisheries resources and fishing technology
5. Aquaculture and blue growth
6. Marine litter, ecotoxicology, and water pollution
7. Marine protected areas, conservation of aquatic resources and ecosystems
8. Environmental education
9. Elasmobranch biodiversity, conservation and management

COMMITTEES

Scientific Committee

- **Dr Mirko Đurović**, University of Montenegro, Institute of Marine Biology, *Chairman of the Scientific Committee*
- **Dr Ali Serhan Tarkan**, Mugla Sıtkı Kosman University, Türkiye
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Conference

- **Dr Radoje Laušević**, *Chair of the Conference*

T1: Marine and freshwater biodiversity, systematics, taxonomy, and data management

Marine Bivalve Molluscs of Montenegro (southeast Adriatic Sea)

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Abstract

Bivalves represent an extremely important component of the marine ecosystems, thus this paper presents an updated inventory of marine bivalves of Montenegro. The checklist based on published literature and recent research includes 165 taxa, summarizing the diversity of the known bivalve species from 1967 to 2020. Eleven species are recorded for the first time in Montenegrin coastal waters (*Bosemprella incarnata*, *Cardites antiquatus*, *Flexopecten hyalinus*, *Glans trapezia*, *Lajonkairia lajonkairii*, *Limaria tuberculata*, *Pandora inaequalis*, *Peronidia albicans*, *Pholas dactylus*, *Pseudochama gryphina* and *Solecurtus strigilatus*). Six species are non-indigenous (*Anadara transversa*, *Arcuatula senhousia*, *Fulvia fragilis*, *Magallana gigas*, *Pinctada imbricata radiata* and *Ruditapes philippinarum*), while one is cryptogenic (*Teredo navalis*). Two species (*Lithophaga lithophaga* and *Pinna nobilis*) are additionally listed in Annex IV of the Habitat Directive and are therefore protected fauna species in Montenegro. Three species (*Lithophaga lithophaga*, *Pinna rudis* and *Pholas dactylus*) are strictly protected according to the Bern Convention (Appendix II), while four species (*Lithophaga lithophaga*, *Pinna nobilis*, *Pinna rudis* and *Pholas dactylus*) are endangered or threatened according to the Barcelona Convention (Annex II). According to the IUCN Red list *Pinna nobilis* is Critically Endangered species. Some species are excluded from the checklist as: *Thyasira orahovaziana*, *Spaniorinus reconditus* and *Mytilus edulis*. Although recently morphological and molecular investigation showed that *Glycymeris glycymeris* in the Adriatic Sea is mistakenly identified, this research included just two localities (Pag Bay and Pašman Channel) in the north Adriatic, so further research are required, thus this species is not excluded from the checklist.

Keywords: new records, native, NIS, bivalvia, Adriatic Sea

Exploring the nutritional potential of *Ulva lactuca* from Boka Kotorska Bay

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Abstract

Seaweeds hold significant promise as a sustainable, nutrient-rich food source with notable health benefits. This study aimed to assess the nutritive potential of *Ulva lactuca* Linnaeus from Boka Kotorska Bay (Adriatic Sea) and explore its potential for commercial purposes. The samples of *Ulva lactuca* were identified, rinsed, dried, and ground into powder for the analysis of their chemical and mineral composition, as well as fatty acid and amino acid profiles. *Ulva* powder was found to contain 19.2% protein, 21.4% ash, and 3.8% lipids. Potassium and calcium were the dominant macro elements, while the micro element content was low. *Ulva* powder had 42.57% saturated fatty acids (SFA), of which palmitic acid was the major SFA. Monounsaturated fatty acids comprised 18.36%, and the level of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) was 38.33%. Alpha-linolenic acid (n-3 PUFA) was the major PUFA at 13.74%, followed by linoleic acid (n-6 PUFA) at 11.26%. The ratio of n-6 to n-3 PUFA was 1.43, considered beneficial for health as these fatty acids cannot be synthesized by the human body and are important for disease prevention. The amino acid profile of *Ulva* powder showed a high content of amino acids (92.65 g/100 g protein), of which essential amino acids (EAA) accounted for 33.19 g/100 g protein, with leucine and lysine being the most abundant. Other significant EAA included valine, isoleucine, phenylalanine, and threonine, while methionine and histidine were the limiting EAA. Non-essential amino acids were 59.46 g/100 g protein, with glutamic acid and aspartic acid being the most prevalent. The amino acid composition of *Ulva* meets WHO and FAO recommendations regarding amino acid requirement patterns. In conclusion, *Ulva lactuca* from Boka Kotorska Bay demonstrates significant nutritive value, making it suitable for human nutrition as a dietary supplement or novel food ingredient. Additionally, it shows promise as a supplementary protein source in fish feed.

This research was supported by the COST action Tomorrow's 'wheat of the sea': *Ulva*, a model for an innovative mariculture (seawheat) CA20106.

Keywords: seaweed, fatty acids, amino acids, food, feed

New data of the endangered species *Theodoxus transversalis* (C. Pfeiffer, 1828) in the lower part of the Danube River

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Abstract

The family Neritidae (Nerites) includes marine, brackish and freshwater taxa that are restricted to tropical regions and the southern hemisphere. An exception is the genus *Theodoxus* Montfort, 1810, a freshwater and brackish water group native to Europe and the Mediterranean. Three species are represented in Serbia: *Theodoxus fluviatilis* (L., 1758), *T. danubialis* and *T. transversalis* (C. Pfeiffer, 1828). *T. transversalis* - striped nerite, has an oval, mostly gray shell with three dark transverse stripes. The operculum is reddish, but lacks the enlarged apophysis plate present in *T. fluviatilis*. This species has been reported as extinct for the upper part of the Danube, while it is extremely rare in the middle and lower parts. It used to be widespread, but due to the declining trend of populations, the species is classified as EN in the IUCN list. Stable populations in Serbia were found in the Velika Morava and Nišava rivers, while in the Danube it only occurred in smaller numbers in the Stari Slankamen locality. Recent field research in November 2023 provided new data for this rare species for the lower part of the Danube, in the Prahovo area. In the coastal zone (up to 1.5 m depth) samples were taken with a benthological hand net from all available microhabitats using the MHS (Multi-Habitat Sampling) technique, in zones with greater depth samples were taken with a benthological dredge. Samples were collected with a dredge by pulling a net across the river bottom over a length of approximately 10 m with 3 transects along the river cross-section. A total of 56 specimens of the striped nerite were found at the Prahovo site, and the stability of the population was determined using the relative abundance scale. Our new results show that the population of *T. transversalis* in the lower part of the Danube in the Prahovo area can be described as high abundance and stable.

This research was funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia; contract No. 451-03-66/2024-03/200007.

Keywords: mollusca, gastropoda, striped nerite, benthological dredge, and Prahovo, Serbia

Lake Prespa: Temporal-Spatial Analysis of Macrozoobenthos and Ecological Status

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Abstract

Lake Prespa is part of a hydrogeological system that includes Lake Ohrid, Mount Galicica, and Lake Prespa itself. It is globally recognized as the oldest, richest, and most diverse permanent lake system in Europe, dating back to the Pliocene epoch. Since the 1990s, persistent anthropogenic impacts, such as unsustainable agricultural practices and irrigation, combined with a constant decrease in water levels due to prolonged dry periods and global climate change, have synergistically transformed the lake. This transformation has turned Lake Prespa into a eutrophic and relatively shallow body of water, adversely affecting water quality and native biodiversity. The purpose of this study was to compare the ecological status of the lake's water over the past seven years (2016-2023). A comparative analysis was conducted using data on the ecological status based on the macrozoobenthos along the depth gradient at three localities in Lake Prespa during the summer seasons of both periods. The study revealed no improvement in the ecological status at all three localities (Konjsko, Stenje, and Krani). In 2018, these localities were assessed with a bad ecological status, and this assessment remained unchanged in 2023. The macrozoobenthos community structure in the summer of 2023 indicated a further decline in both population density and species diversity across all three localities.

Keywords: Lake Prespa, macrozoobenthos, ecological status, community structure

The state of the macrophyte vegetation in Prespa Lake in the last decade (2014-2024)

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Abstract

The macrophyte vegetation has a significant role in the circulation of the substances in the littoral zone of Lake Prespa. Macrophyte plants are important producers of oxygen, they are natural mechanical and biological filters of lake water. They also provide food, habitat and shelter for many invertebrate and vertebrate organisms from the coastal zone. The qualitative composition and abundance of macrophyte vegetation are one of the most relevant indicators for the quality of the water ecosystem. This group of organisms is characterized by a wide range of environmental tolerances and preferences that characterize indicators of water quality over a long period of time. The constant and extensive withdrawal of water from the Lake Prespa, the cumulative anthropogenic pressure and increased nutrient load, as well as the changes in the climate have also impacted the macrophyte vegetation in the lake, which is best reflected in its biodiversity and abundance. To assess the present status of the macrophyte vegetation in Prespa Lake, a comparison of the results from the past decade has been undertaken. Thus, the results from the research on the qualitative composition of macrophyte species and their abundance in 2014, 2022 and 2024, in locality Oteshevo have been compared. The results showed a huge difference in the diversity of macrophytes, as well as in their abundance at different depth points. The highest number of registered macrophytes was recorded in 2012 (13 in total), followed by 8 macrophyte species in 2022, and the lowest number of registered macrophytes in 2024 (only 4).

Keywords: Lake Prespa, macrophyte vegetation, biodiversity, abundance

Towed camera as the main ground truthing methods during Croatian marine coastal and benthic habitats mapping

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Abstract

Project of benthic and coastal habitat mapping for 51% of Croatian marine waters is finished by the end of 2023. In total, 30,278 km² were mapped, with approximately 6,600 km² by direct mapping using acoustic methods (multibeam and side-scan sonar) for marine areas deeper than 15 m, and remote sensing (Sentinel-2 satellite imagery and digital ortho-photo images) for coastal and benthic habitats down to 15 m deep. Remaining area of 23,617 km² is modeled with an artificial neural network-based model using historical and newly obtained sediment and habitat type data. A direct mapping was applied on the entire seabed down to 40 m, the entire seabed within MPAs, as well as Natura 2000 sites and selected areas of particular interest. At a minimum, habitats were mapped at the 3rd classification level, while priority, endangered, and rare habitat types were mapped at the 4th and 5th levels when possible. In situ field validation was applied at more than 4,200 sites using ground truthing methods such as scuba diving and the use of ROVs, towed cameras, coastal observations, UAVs, and corers for granulometry. Mapping project was realized in a period of only 25 months. To obtain large scale gathering of in situ information, the most effective was towed camera method. We developed simplified but highly functional towed camera and an online spatial database for video analysis, geotagging, and exporting data in GIS format for further processing. The camera (GoPro) is installed within a stainless steel frame to provide protection, which is equipped with two fins, a red filter for shallow depths, two lights for larger depths, and a digital scuba depth meter positioned within the camera's field of view. The towed camera is mostly handheld using a 7 mm rope from a 3,7 m inflatable boat with an 18 hp engine. While a surface monitoring option is not provided, this simplified system produces minimal drag. That allowed using onboard GPS logger with sufficient spatial precision. Most video transects surveyed the sea floor from 2–50 m depth, while transects obtained from research vessel were collected for deeper bottoms to a maximum depth of 130 m. Our towed camera and GIS database enabled us to record and analyze over 3,700 video transects in less than two years, making it the primary method for large-scale in situ validation.

Keywords: habitat mapping, ground truthing, towed camera, spatial database

The pipe of life: peculiarities of a gorgonian assemblages in Boka Kotorska Bay (Montenegro)

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Abstract

In Boka Kotorska Bay (Montenegro), heavy anthropogenic pressures co-occur with peculiar environmental conditions due to fresh underwater springs. In this unique habitat, some branched anthozoans act as the main habitat engineers, producing a strong three-dimensionality of the habitat. In particular, the iron tubes of two pipelines laid at Opatovo in 1989 host an extraordinary community of colonial cnidarians, mainly composed of the gorgonian *Leptogorgia sarmentosa*. To study this unique community, photographic surveys were carried out in 2023 at depths ranging from 20 to 35 meters. In total, 409 colonies were counted, reaching a maximum density of 21.2 specimens per square meter. The maximal height of the colonies settled on the pipelines was 112 cm, while the average height was 51 ± 0.12 cm. Based on the age of the artificial substrate, it is possible to infer a maximal growth rate of 3.2 cm per year. The color range of these populations included red (62%) and orange (38%) specimens, with no yellow or white colonies observed. Signs of damage and/or many epiphytes were recorded on more than 15% of colonies, and 10 specimens were found dead. Together with *L. sarmentosa*, the rare whip coral *Spinimuricea klavereni*, the stolonifer *Sarcodictyon catenatum*, the zoanthids *Epizoanthus* sp., and *Parazoanthus axinellae*, and the scleractinian *Caryophyllia inornata* and *C. schmitii* compose this unique assemblage. The high productivity of the bay, due to the significant inflow of continental waters from numerous seasonal creeks and the underwater karst springs, is responsible for the extremely dense populations of passive filter feeders and the very high growth rate observed in the sea fans. These peculiarities confirm the recent Montenegrin government's decision to establish two protected zones in the Boka Kotorska Bay and suggest that such areas should be progressively expanded.

Keywords: anthozoans, vrulja, habitat engineers, conservation, Mediterranean Sea

Sponges extracts from the Adriatic Sea induces apoptosis on HeLa cells

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Abstract

Marine sponges are a rich source of unique biomolecules with significant pharmaceutical potential, including anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial compounds. Researchers extract these biomolecules from sponges to develop new drugs and therapies due to their diverse and potent bioactive properties. The sustainable harvesting and cultivation of marine sponges are crucial for the continued exploration and utilization of these valuable natural resources. Reviewing existing literature and distribution maps, it was decided to conduct research on three species of sponges (*Axinella cannabina*, *Aplysina aerophoba*, and *Sarcotragus spinosulus*), due to their ecological significance, prevalence in Montenegrin waters, and potential for yielding bioactive compounds. These species were selected based on the abundant populations in the south-east Adriatic's Boka Kotorska Bay, and their previously exhibited high cytotoxicity toward HeLa cells. These species were further investigated for the mechanism of their cytotoxicity. Supercritical CO₂ extraction was used to obtain extracts from these sponges. Flow cytometry determined the proportion of HeLa cells in each stage of the cell cycle after staining with propidium iodide dye. Additionally, acridine orange and ethidium bromide staining were employed to visualize the type of cell death under a fluorescence microscope. In both experiments, HeLa cells were treated with IC₅₀ and 2xIC₅₀ concentrations for 24 h and 48 h. The best results were shown by *S. spinosulus* sponge extracts, which exhibited time- and concentration-dependent effects on HeLa cells. Flow cytometry revealed the accumulation of HeLa cells in the sub-G1 phase of the cell cycle after incubation with the extracts. The proapoptotic effect was confirmed in HeLa cells after fluorescence microscopy analysis, showing that the extracts induced visible signs of apoptosis. In conclusion, the tested extracts exhibited a proapoptotic effect on HeLa cells.

Keywords: sponge, apoptosis, HeLa cells, Adriatic sea, anti-tumor

Diversity of marine life in the coastal zone of the Hilandar Monastery (Mount Athos, Greece)

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Abstract

The Institute for Nature Conservation of Serbia, with the blessing of the Most Reverend Archimandrite Methodius, Abbot of the Holy Serbian Imperial Lavra Hilandar, conducted a study of the natural values of the domain of the Hilandar Monastery on Mount Athos in Greece from 2015 to 2018. As part of the multidisciplinary research, biodiversity studies were carried out on the Aegean coast in spring and fall 2017 and in summer 2018, and resumed in spring 2024. Along the marine zone, where steep, rocky coasts alternate with pebbly and sandy bays, the marine life in the bays around the Hilandar pier was photographed and then determined using a robust, waterproof 14 MP Olympus TG-810 camera. A variety of species were found in the well-preserved coastal area with no significant sources of pollution, including algae (*Acetabularia acetabulum*, *Padina pavonica*), sponges (*Aplysina aerophoba*, *Hemimycale columella*, *Chondrosia reniformis*, *Scarispongia scalaris*), corals and anemones (*Actinia equina*, *Aiptasia mutabilis*, *Anemonia viridis*, *Cereus pedunculatus*, *Cerianthus membranaceus*, *Chondrilla nucula*, *Cladocora caespitosa*, *Condylactis aurantiaca*), aquatic plants (*Posidonia oceanica*), hydrozoans, polychaetes (*Protula tubularia*, *Sabella spalanzanii*), molluscs (mussels: *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Ostrea edulis*, *Pinna nobilis*; gastropods: *Flabellina affinis*, *Patella* sp., *Phorcus turbinatus*; chitons: *Chiton* sp.; cephalopods: *Octopus vulgaris*), crustaceans (*Clibanarius erythropus*, *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*, *Palaemon elegans*), echinoderms (starfish: *Echinaster sepositus*, sea urchins: *Arbacia lixula*, *Paracentrotus lividus*, *Sphaerechinus granularis*; sea cucumbers: *Holothuria tubulosa*), fish (*Chromis*, *Coris julis*, *Dicentrarchus labrax*, *Diplodus puntazzo*, *D. vulgaris*, *D. sargus*, *Gobius bucchichi*, *G. cobitis*, *Lithognathus mormyrus*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Oblada melanura*, *Parablennius gattorugine*, *Sarpa salpa*, *Serranus scriba*, *Symphodus cinereus*, *Sparus aurata*, *Thalassoma pavo*, *Tripterygion tripteronotus*, *T. delaisi*, etc.).

Keywords: marine biodiversity, Mount Athos, Hilandar

Summer zooplankton community composition in the South Adriatic Sea (Lastovo Island)

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Abstract

During a two-week July survey in southern Adriatic, Lastovo Island, we investigated microzooplankton and mesozooplankton diversity using traditional light microscopy (LM) and metabarcoding of the 18S rRNA gene. Samples were collected from two pore-sized net tows (53 µm and 200 µm) and two depth layers. Species richness and evenness showed higher median values within the deep layer and microzooplankton, while phylogenetic richness was higher for the surface layer and mesozooplankton. Beta diversity (weighted UniFrac, PERMANOVA test) indicated significant differences between fractions (p -value = 0.021). The community was predominantly Metazoa (80% in micro- vs. 55% in meso- fraction), followed by mostly heterotrophic and parasitic Dinoflagellata (7.5% in micro- vs. 12% in meso- fraction), Fungi (5% in micro- vs. 14% in meso- fraction), and Ciliophora in mesozooplankton (7.8%). Other groups in microzooplankton (Ciliophora, Chlorophyta, Stramenopiles, and Cercozoa) had less than 2% relative abundance, while autotrophs and mixotrophs were scarce (mostly within Chlorophyta and Gyrista, 2.9% and 2%, respectively). Class Copepoda dominated with *Centropages typicus*, *Oithona similis*, *Oithona atlantica*, *Paracalanus parvus parvus* and *Temora discaudata*. Generally, *Centropages*, *Oithona*, and the larvae of brachiopod *Phoronis* were more abundant in deep layers, while unclassified Copepoda, *Paracalanus*, *Temora*, and *Mecynocera* were more abundant in surface layers. Light microscopy analysis identified dominant genera including *Evadne*, *Pseudevadne*, *Centropages*, *Temora*, *Oithona*, *Oncaea*, *Corycaeus*, and *Oikopleura*. In mesozooplankton, cladoceran *Evadne spinifera*, copepod *Paracalanus parvus parvus*, and *Oithona similis* had higher abundances in surface layers, contributing to overall dissimilarity between layers (SIMPER test = 65.36%). Notably, metabarcoding did not record LM-dominant *Evadne* and had identified *Corycaeus* as rare, while *O. atlantica* and *T. discaudata* were not identified with LM, indicating a need for further curation and taxonomical annotation of genotyped databases.

Keywords: marine and freshwater biodiversity, systematics, taxonomy and data management

Preliminary diet analysis of European eel, *Anguilla anguilla* (Linnaeus, 1758) from Lake Skadar (Montenegro)

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Abstract

Transition from freshwater to saltwater and vice versa presents multiple challenges for catadromous European eel and survival during these critical moments is largely conditioned by the quality of diet, especially during the freshwater life-stage. Despite this, the diet composition and survival of European eel is poorly studied in Montenegro, especially in Lake Skadar which is an important area for this species. In this study we analyzed the diet of 50 European eels, captured in Lake Skadar during 2020-2021. Results suggest that the diet of European eel during freshwater life-stage in Lake Skadar mainly consisted of *Unio* sp. (Bivalvia), Odonata, Polichaeta, Oligochaeta, Hirudinea, and some cyprinid fish species. However, diet varied among length classes and sex. The most abundant group of prey were Bivalvia, while the most numerous group were Odonata. As the body length increases, the diet of European eel becomes more diverse. The individuals about 50 cm in length prefer feeding on fish, which is in agreement with the available literature data. This study suggests that the eel is more of an opportunistic predator that feeds on available organisms rather than being specialized for the predation of a specific group of organisms. What is evident is that, as the eel grows, its diet is dominated by available smaller fish species, mainly those that are most abundant in Lake Skadar. Future research should be oriented towards the seasonal dynamics of the eel's diet in Lake Skadar to gain insight into whether there is any preference for its prey during different seasons.

Keywords: condition, European eel, males, females, length classes

Novel approach for surveying habitatypes and organisms on the seabed

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Abstract

The study of benthic macrofauna provides a good opportunity to assess the state of health of marine environment. The majority of benthic animals are sedentary, with particular reference to epifauna, and could thus serve as an environmental memory of different disturbances. Traditionally, the study of macrobenthic epifauna on the sedimentary bottom is performed by the use of specific dredge. Nowadays, when such approach is considered as destructive and causing considerable damages to the sea bottom biota, novel non-destructive methods are preferred. The epifauna of the coastal detritic bottom in the Slovenian sea was studied using two different methods, the traditional method of sampling with dredge which was additionally equipped with video cameras, and a specially designed video sledge. Testing of the two methods revealed that they are both suitable for macroepifauna sampling as they provide us with a wide range of data on the epibenthic community. On the other hand, they also give us a bit different aspect on the community. With samples from dredge taxonomic determination is more thorough and precise and we could get insight about smaller sized and hidden species. We can also directly assess biomass of the community. With videosledge we could obtain good information about distribution and abundance of bigger taxa in the area and their behaviour. We also obtain other different information about the seabed like its morphology and presence of physical damages. A range of data is obtained with almost no disturbance and no destruction in a relatively short time and with a large area being surveyed. Besides this obtained visual data are permanent and can be archived. We concluded that the video sledge method can provide a good insight into the structure of the epibenthic community of coastal detritic bottom.

Keywords: epibenthos, video sledge, dredge

The Project “Puglia FishLifeStyle”: Biological characteristics and ecology of the main resources for Puglia fishery

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Abstract

The project “Puglia FishLifeStyle” (EMFF operational programmes 2014 – 2020) was financed with the aim of supporting the Apulian fishery products, also considering the environmental quality of the areas in which the fish was caught, activating a series of evaluation, information and divulgation to increase the conscious and sustainable consumer approach. ARPA Puglia was a partner in the project, with the coordination function, together with CIHEAM Bari and the *Health Marketplace* structure of the Puglia Region. According to WP2 of the project, ARPA Puglia was entrusted for the reporting activity on the “Biological characteristics and ecology of the main resources for Puglia fishery”, whose output was a booklet which contains descriptive sheets for 116 fish species, chosen from those mostly caught and/or most valuable for the Apulian fishery. The sheets contain information on the biological, ecological and other general characteristics (including the state of exploitation and nutritional facts) of the identified species, taken from the available and accessible literature on the topic, making them as accessible as possible even to non-expert people. Moreover, with the main aim of the widest dissemination, and with the ultimate aim of promoting an informed approach to the final consumers of fish products, a 100 x 70 cm poster was created in which there are photographic images of the 116 fish species, with the respective QR codes (accessible from smartphones) which link to the individual sheets of the booklet; the posters have been distributed and are available on request both for commercial operators in the fishery field and other potentially interested stakeholders.

Keywords: fishery resources, fisheries biology, taxonomy, consumer education

Novel approaches for the monitoring of freshwater bodies

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Abstract

Inland waterbodies and wetland habitats are extremely important in terms of biodiversity conservation. Thanks to the abundance of water surrounded by karst-hilly terrain, the biological diversity in Vrana Lake in Croatia, Deran Lake in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Skadar Lake in Montenegro is extremely valuable. Water quality in these areas are deteriorating as a result of technological advancements, industrial production, agricultural activities, and rapid urbanization. The water environment serves as a source of food and drink, allows for agriculture, production, recreation, and tourism, and accepts large amounts of water, potentially preventing floods. For the better biodiversity preservation in the lakes we propose a water quality monitoring by hybrid data collection from different sensors approach. Our approach gave a simpler and effective novel monitoring tool for the protection of the selected freshwater bodies.

Keywords: freshwater, monitoring, novel tools

Research trends and collaborative practices: preliminary results from a FAO AdriaMed-ASFA case study

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Abstract

The FAO AdriaMed Project has been active since 1999 and involves Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Italy, Montenegro, and Slovenia. The objectives of the Project include the provision of technical assistance to participating countries for the sustainable development of aquaculture and fishing activities considering the interests of the local fishing and farming communities, the protection of the aquatic environment and the enhancement of positive interaction between fisheries and aquaculture, thus promoting the achievement of the FAO Four Betters. AdriaMed also aims at promoting scientific and institutional cooperation among participating countries as a baseline for discussion toward the development of sustainable aquaculture and fisheries. In 2024, the AdriaMed Project in cooperation with the ASFA Secretariat (Aquatic Sciences and Fisheries Abstracts) launched an *ad-hoc* project to evaluate research trends in Adriatic countries in the past 25 years (1999 – 2024) and to understand the evolution of collaborative practices. The *ad-hoc* project is also aimed at providing elements to assess the impact and effectiveness of the AdriaMed Project network on the evolution of cooperative research in the Adriatic Sea. The *ad-hoc* project is within the activities that ASFA is launching with its regional networks to enhance knowledge sharing. A search methodology was agreed to identify relevant marine fisheries research. Resources relevant to search criteria were identified through online searches on different sources (ASFA, Web of Science) and local and national held collections (library catalogs, institutional repositories). The relevant references were used to build a collection on OpenASFA. These results are being analyzed to understand the research trends, with particular attention paid to collaborative practices among authors and the final aim to understand trends in scientific cooperation and knowledge sharing in the Adriatic region.

Keywords: international cooperation, aquatic sciences, fisheries, research, bibliometric analysis, data management

Effects of coal mining activities and photovoltaic power plant operation towards the macroinvertebrate community in Oslomej reservoir and river Temnica (R. North Macedonia)

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Abstract

Coal mining and photovoltaic power plant operation can significantly impact the macroinvertebrate communities in freshwater ecosystems due to changes in water quality and habitat structure resulting from dramatic erosion processes. Therefore, monitoring the macroinvertebrate community serves as an important indicator of ecological health. The observed changes in species composition, abundance and diversity signal the broader impacts of coal mining and photovoltaic power plant operation, providing essential information for conservation and remediation efforts. This study presents the ecosystem conditions in Oslomej reservoir and river Temnica based on the aquatic invertebrate community. Aquatic invertebrate sampling was conducted on Oslomej reservoir and river Temnica in the vicinity of the former coal mine “Oslomej”. The benthic community in Oslomej reservoir was characterized with significantly low abundance of aquatic invertebrates presented with scarce populations of aquatic mollusks (*Peregriana peregra*), aquatic worms (*Limnodrilus hoffmeisteri*), crustaceans (*Gammarus balcanicus* and *Astacus astacus*), chironomids (*Orthocladius thienemanni*, *Tanytus punctipennis*, *Cladotanytarsus mancus* and *Chironomus plumosus*), mayflies (*Cloeon dipterum*) and damselflies (*Lestes virens*). On the other hand, the diversity of aquatic invertebrates in river Temnica was shown to be slightly higher, comprised by aquatic mollusks, annelids, mayflies, caddisflies, dragonflies, aquatic bugs, beetles and true flies. The obtained results showed that Oslomej reservoir and river Temnica suffer habitat degradation and put up with different pollutants, probably introduced through the soil and sediment that entered the reservoir and the river during the construction of the PV Oslomej 3 on the deforested mining area, as well as from previous acid mine drainage from the coal mine “Oslomej”.

Keywords: macroinvertebrates, biodiversity assessment, ecosystem health, Macedonia

The impact of small hydropower plants on stone crayfish *Austropotamobius torrentium* (Schrank 1803)

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Abstract

The benefits of small hydropower plants as a renewable source of electricity production are well known, but there is also a need to recognize that they can significantly affect the ecological functions of rivers and adjacent habitats in which they are located. The following research presents the impact of ten small hydropower plants (SHPPs) located in western and eastern part of R. North Macedonia towards the stone crayfish *Austropotamobius torrentium* and its habitats in the affected river ecosystems. All the investigated SHPPs are built on water courses in pristine conditions which provide well conserved habitats for occurrence of endemic and rare species, as well as species important for conservation, such as the stone crayfish. The results presented in this study show that the sampling sites above the intakes remained in favorable and undisturbed conditions. Good populations of *A. torrentium* whose conservation requires designation of Special Areas of Conservation within the Natura 2000 network occurred above intakes, as the hydrological regime has not changed. Stone crayfish populations significantly changed in the river stretches between the intakes and the powerhouses, confirming the harmful impact of the investigated SHPPs. Probably, habitat fragmentation, hydropeaking events, long-term dried conditions or activities during the construction and the operational phase caused severe drop in the abundance of the stone crayfish, even its disappearance. Bearing in mind the high vulnerability of the stone crayfish, we suggest that the species could be used as very important indicators of the detrimental impact of SHPPs.

Keywords: small hydropower plant, aquatic ecosystems, stone crayfish, impact, R. North Macedonia

Ecological research of ichthyofauna and benthic fauna in Kozjak reservoir

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Abstract

Kozjak reservoir is the largest artificial one in Republic of North Macedonia, created by a dam building in Treska River. As a reservoir with a great depth, phytoplankton biomass and primary production offers excellent conditions for existence of a large number of fish species and benthic communities. The aim of this study was to determine the composition of the ichthyofauna and benthic fauna communities. The results of seasonal research conducted in 2023 showed the presence of eleven fish species. Nine fish species were autochthonous for Vardar River basin, while *Carassius gibelio* and *Pseudorasbora parva* were allochthonous and invasive fish species. The research of the benthic fauna community presented domination of polysaprobic tubificid species *Tubifex tubifex* and *Limnodrilus hoffmeisteri*. The study results contribute to ecological research of the ichthyofauna communities and benthic fauna in recently formed reservoirs. Such insights are of great benefit pointing the presence and rapid increase in densities and presence of allochthonous and invasive fish species in the reservoir. As aquatic ecosystems are related to aquatic macroinvertebrates representing a heterogeneous collection of evolutionary diverse taxa that makes them particularly provocative for this study.

Keywords: ichthyofauna, benthic fauna, Kozjak reservoir, ecological research

Overview of stoneflies diversity patterns in Serbian hilly and mountain streams

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Abstract

Stoneflies (Plecoptera) as a significant component of running water ecosystems are intolerant to variation in their environmental conditions. This study included 44 sites of hilly and mountainous streams with predominantly hard bottom substrate classified according to Serbian national legislation as WBT3 - altitude up to 500 m, WBT4 - altitude above 500 m and WBT6 - small streams not covered by legislation. Macroinvertebrate samples were collected during 2019 with a hand net using the kick and sweep sampling method according to European standards (EN 27828:1994). Stoneflies were sorted out, identified and diversity analyses were performed using FLORA software vr. 2013. Stoneflies were recorded as a significant component of the community at all sampling sites. They were represented by 6 families and 18 taxa. The species *Leuctra* gr. *hippopus*, *Protonemura montana* and *Siphonoperla torrentium* were the most numerous among the Plecoptera. Shannon entropy, species richness and equitability were used to describe alpha diversity of stoneflies in different WBTs. The highest values of the analyzed components were found in WBT4. Slightly lower values were observed in WBT6, while the components of alpha diversity showed lower values in WBT3. The total beta diversity and its components were analyzed using the methods described by Baselga. The Plecoptera community in WBT6 showed the lowest value for nestedness with the highest species turnover, indicating the highest beta diversity. In WBT3, the nestedness component was slightly higher, but species turnover was low and overall beta diversity had the lowest values within the three WBTs analyzed. At WBT4, the values showed the lowest species turnover and the highest nestedness, indicating that the overall beta diversity was higher at altitudes above 500 meters. Lower values of alpha and beta diversity of the Plecoptera community at WBT3 suggest that the sites at altitudes below 500 m were exposed to higher anthropogenic pressure.

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Keywords: stoneflies, diversity, alpha diversity, beta diversity, hilly and mountain streams, Serbia

Zooplankton Dynamics in Relation to Island-Trapped Waves Near Lastovo Island (Adriatic Sea)

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate zooplankton abundance and diversity near Lastovo Island, where island-trapped waves (ITWs) are known to affect physical and biological conditions. Zooplankton were sampled up to four times daily (6h, 12h, 18h, 23h) from July 13 to 22, in two water layers: the surface (above the thermocline) and the deep layer (below the thermocline). Samples were preserved in a 4% formaldehyde seawater solution for later microscopic analysis. The Mann-Whitney test revealed significant statistical differences in zooplankton abundances across different mesh sizes, particularly for smaller size fractions. Initial high densities of microzooplankton were observed from July 13 to 15, followed by a significant decline in both layers. Copepod nauplii were the dominant group, constituting 35–56% of total microzooplankton, while calanoid copepodites contributed 8–23%. Notable tintinnid diversity included *Tintinnopsis radix*, *Codonellopsis schabi*, and *Tintinnopsis levigata*. A total of 80 mesozooplankton taxa were identified: 72 in the surface layer and 73 in the deep layer, with 10 taxa representing over 50% of the community. Copepods, particularly *Paracalanus parvus*, accounted for 70%, followed by *Centropages typicus*, *Temora stylifera*, and *Oithona similis*. Cladocerans (*Evadne spinifera* and *Pseudevadne tergestina*) and appendicularians (*Oikopleura longicauda*) were also frequently observed. Patterns in pico and nano fractions showed a decline until July 17, followed by an increase, reflecting micro and nanophytoplankton trends in the upper layer. In contrast, the meso fraction (calanoids 200 µm) and omnivores exhibited no clear trends. Overall, the timing of sampling did not reveal consistent patterns, though higher values were generally found in the upper layer. Mesozooplankton did not show a clear response to ITWs, suggesting that while ITWs may enhance nutrient availability and influence microzooplankton dynamics, their impact on mesozooplankton communities is less pronounced.

Keywords: Microzooplankton, mesozooplankton, Island-trapped waves

Boka Kotorska Bay as a potential Natura 2000 site

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Abstract

The concept behind the Natura 2000 network is to harmonize the coexistence of the people and nature, with special attention to requirements from EU Habitat and Bird Directives. Creation of Natura 2000 network in Montenegro is one of the obligations as a closing benchmark that Montenegro has to fulfill from Chapter 27. One of the first necessary steps is mapping of marine habitats and protected species distribution and that was the aim of this work in the Boka Kotorska (81.8 km²). To assess the typology and distribution of marine habitats as well as presence and abundance of protected species SCUBA diving and ROV visual census were implemented in combination with the Side Scan Sonar survey. Interpretation of habitat types of importance for the EU (so-called Natura habitats) showed the presence of 7 types of Natura habitats. Three of these habitats exhibited very good representativeness: Muddy and sandy seabeds that are not covered by seawater during low tide, Large shallow coves and bays and Underwater sea reefs. Good representativeness has been assessed for Shallow permanently submerged sandy seabeds, *Posidonia oceanica* meadows and Estuaries, while Semi-submersed marine caves are not representative in the bay. For all recorded habitats, the relationship with the EUNIS categorization of habitats as well as the size of areas in hectares is calculated. Furthermore in the Boka Kotorska Bay during surveys in 2023 and from the literature, presence of protected 12 species of flora, 35 invertebrate, 10 fish, 2 sea turtles and 2 marine mammals has been registered. In conclusion, the Boka Kotorska Bay represents an unique area with high biodiversity and unfortunately with also high anthropogenic pressures, so proclamation of this bay as a Natura 2000 site (or even a more strictly marine protected area) along with appropriate management would be necessary as soon as possible.

The Agency of environmental protection is the financier and owner of the data.

Keywords: Natura 2000, habitat mapping, EUNIS

T2: Climate change and impacts to marine ecosystem

Trends of sea level, air temperature and precipitations in the Mediterranean, according to the Med-CORDEX and Euro-CORDEX simulations of future climate scenarios

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Abstract

In the frame of the Euro-MED MedSeaRise (Supporting Adaptation to Mediterranean Sea Level Rise) project, a specific action is voted to identify and retrieve outputs of climate scenarios simulations that are suitable to study the future climate evolution over the Mediterranean, during the current Century. At this stage of the project implementation, two main sources of simulations outputs have been identified, namely the Euro-CORDEX (<https://www.euro-cordex.net/>) and the Med-CORDEX (<https://www.medcordex.eu/>). From those regional models dataset, ensembles of time series of air temperature, precipitation and sea level fields have been extracted matching a domain covering the entire Mediterranean region. The three main future climate scenarios have been considered, RCP2.6, RCP4.0 and RCP8.5, to study the features of the climate evolution in six specific coastal areas, which are distributed across the basin. This work shows the sensitivity of each selected field to the future radiative forcing and it evaluates the uncertainty associated to the climate projections, thanks to the analysis of the ensemble model outputs. Furthermore, key points of the time series evolution are highlighted and discussed in the frame of the adaptation and resilience applications. In fact, according to the MedSeaRise objectives, the elaborated data are going to be used as inputs in the evaluation of the risks associated to the increase of the sea level for chosen classes of impacts affecting anthropic activities or ecosystems. To this end, the time series of the atmospheric and sea fields are prepared to be used to conduct case studies and to produce benchmarks. The adopted approach is going to be explained in detail too and the preliminary project results summarized.

This work has been carried on with the contribution from the EU co-financing and the Interreg Euro-MED Programme, in the frame of MedSeaRise Project”.

Keywords: climate change, climate change impacts, sea level trend, risk assessment methodology

MedSeaRise: a step further in understanding how to face the risks related to the progressive increase of sea level in the Mediterranean

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Abstract

Climate change is evident in many aspects, among them there is the progressive increase of the average sea level, which is affecting the rare extremes too, both on their frequency and intensity. The assessment of risks deriving from sea level variations requires a robust quantification of all the elements bringing the sea level to become a hazard, thus, for an effective adaptation to future sea conditions, it is mandatory to have reliable knowledge on scenarios for sea level trends. This is the challenge addressed by MedSeaRise (Supporting Adaptation to Mediterranean Sea Level Rise) project with the objective of improving the assessment of risks deriving from the Mediterranean Sea level variations, through a robust quantification of its hazardous source. So far, the project recognizes that Mediterranean coastal impacts have been deduced from global sea level trends or climate simulation, each affected by significant uncertainties that stimulate a still open debate in the scientific community. As a consequence, there is an urgent need to quantify the likelihood of available scientific information on the expected XXI century sea level trends, in the Mediterranean sub-basins, with an estimate of the uncertainties. MedSeaRise outputs are expected to contribute in meeting this need, defining best practices on sea level trends usage, in the risk assessment processes, according to the sensitivity of impacts to the hazard information likelihood. Best practices are supported by examples of applications and summary datasets, to help stakeholders to flow the scientific information into the risk assessment logic. This work presents the project structure and objectives together with the results achieved to date and the interaction of the project with other research initiatives and projects focused on the climate change effects on the Adriatic basin.

MedSeaRise is a EU co-financing and Interreg Euro-MED Programme study project.

Keywords: climate change, climate change risks, adaptation, European projects, Euro-MED

State of gelatinous zooplankton research in the Adriatic Sea

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Abstract

While crustacean invaders, such as the copepod *Pseudodiaptomus marinus*, are receiving much attention, gelatinous zooplankton is not getting the recognition it deserves until it starts to dramatically influence the environment, as seen with the intrusion of the ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi*. The likely reason for this neglect of gelatinous zooplankton is the low number of experts in the field, as well as the complex identification processes, which are often too intricate for non-specialists. Gelatinous zooplankton has been proven to be a valuable indicator of hydroclimatic changes. In the past decades, more than 20 new gelatinous zooplankton species have been recorded in the Adriatic. This has been correlated with decadal changes in the prevailing types of incoming currents (either from the western or eastern Mediterranean), as well as a constant rise in salinity and temperature, which are altering the thermohaline properties of the Adriatic. Some of these newly recorded species are now established and have become a part of the Adriatic zooplankton fauna, while others are recorded intermittently, depending on the prevailing type of entering currents. In addition to the newly recorded species, six species new to science have been described in the Adriatic, three of which are large scyphomedusae. Recently, metabarcoding methods have been introduced in gelatinous zooplankton research and are being evaluated against classical microscopy-based methods. Metabarcoding is a promising technique that could make monitoring for new species much easier. However, the downside of this method is that it requires curated reference databases and primers suited for detecting the species of interest. One of the advantages of the metabarcoding approach is its ability to detect cryptic invasions, which microscopy-based methods are unable to do.

Keywords: gelatinous zooplankton, allochthonous species, hydroclimatic changes, metabarcoding

T3: Aquatic alien and invasive species

Investigating consumer attitudes and market trading of edible marine invasive alien species in the Greek seafood market

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Abstract

Marine invasive alien species (IAS) are spreading in the Mediterranean Sea, altering species composition and reshaping marine ecosystems. Two questionnaires were prepared, one for identifying consumer preferences on edible IAS, in particular lionfish and blue crab and one for investigating the views of fisheries product traders on the potential marketing perspectives of the above-mentioned species. Comprehending the factors that influence IAS consumption and recording consumer behaviors are essential for directing a marketing approach. The majority of participants expressed support for the following: (a) considering that IAS are harming the marine environment (54%); (b) eating IAS products if it is promoted in a cooking show (61%); (c) buying and consuming IAS as long as they safeguarded indigenous species and the marine environment (63%); and (d) carrying a quality control certificate or a special quality seal (79%). The most important criteria for consumers in the potential purchase of lionfish and blue crabs were freshness, hygienic conditions and whether the species is poisonous. The positive attitude of consumers towards fish quality certification and other quality issues was an important indicator for addressing structural problems in the production and marketing of fisheries products and the significance of advancing a market that could enhance fisheries sustainability and impede the spread of IAS.

Keywords: consumer perceptions, Mediterranean, fish market, fisheries, social norms

Sexual and Seasonal Approaches to Biological Indices of the Invasive Fish Species Red Cornetfish (*Fistularia petimba* Lacepède, 1803) on the Eastern Mediterranean Coasts (Türkiye)

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Abstract

The species *Fistularia petimba* Lacepède, 1803, commonly found on the eastern Mediterranean coasts of Turkey, is an invasive fish species. In this study, six body indices were determined: FI-Stomach Fullness Index, HSI-Hepatosomatic Index, GSI-Gonadosomatic Index, VSI-Visceral Index, Fulton-K: Fulton-Condition, EQ-Encephalization Index, and Brain Weight-BW. A total of 234 specimens, caught as non-target species by trawl boats in the autumn, winter, and summer seasons of 2023, were studied. The average indices (Mean±Sd) were determined according to sex and season. The FI value is higher in females (1.48±0.12) and peaks in the autumn season (2.25 ±0.58). The HSI value is higher in females (0.61±0.05) and peaks in the summer season (1.05± 0.18). The GSI is higher in female individuals (1.42± 0.11), peaking in the summer season (5.25± 0.42). The VSI value is higher in females (4.92± 0.39), with the highest value in the summer season (8.34±1.41). However, the Fulton-K value is similar between males and females, with all individuals having high condition values during the summer period (0.06± 0.01). The EQ value is similar across sexes and seasons. When evaluating BW, it was found that female brain weights are higher than males (0.016 ±0.01), with the highest weights observed in the winter season (0.16±0.01). Among all indices, GSI, Fulton-K, and EQ values show statistical differences in terms of sex (p<0.05). These index results indicate that the red cornetfish, an invasive species, maintains high vitality on the eastern Mediterranean coasts of Turkey. Despite being categorized as Least Concern (LC) in the IUCN Red List 2023, fishing records suggest it threatens the feeding and breeding areas of local fish species. This study demonstrates that the high values in the biological indices of the Lessepsian species over three seasons provide important regional data for fishery management.

Keywords: Lessepsian fish, Red cornetfish, somatic growth, eastern Mediterranean.

New, additional frequent record of invasive species of lionfish (*Pterois miles*) on the Montenegrin coast, Adriatic Sea

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Abstract

Climatic changes occurring in the marine ecosystem are very present and visible. The best indicator of these changes are new species that have not been in our sea until now, which we label as bioindicators. So far, 9 new, invasive species of fish and 2 species of crabs have been recorded in the Montenegrin coast. From February 2023 until now, the presence of 6 individuals of lionfish (*Pterois miles*), an Indo-Pacific species that has reached the Mediterranean and the Adriatic Sea through the Suez Canal, has been recorded. The first find was recorded in 2019 on the shores of the island of Brač, in Croatia. The fish is dangerous because of its poisonous spines, it reproduces all year round and has almost no natural enemies. An increase in the number of this species is expected, and since it directly affects domestic fish species, feeding on the eggs and juvenile stages of those species, it represents a great danger to the ecosystem. Attention must be paid to this problem as soon as possible, and experience shows that the targeted catch of this species is one of the possible solutions for controlling the abundance of this species. Therefore, the coordination of competent ministries and scientific institutes is necessary, in order to respond adequately as soon as possible and try to prevent the rapid spread of this species in our part of the Adriatic Sea through the Action Plan of measures and activities. Of course, coordination of activities at the level of state institutions and scientists of the Adriatic Sea is also necessary.

Keywords: invasive species, climate change, biodiversity, Montenegrin coast

eDNA - A modern tool for the preservation of marine ecosystems: the example of the sea of Montenegro

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Abstract

The Mediterranean region is one of the most responsive to climate change in the world. The increase in air and sea surface water temperatures and salinity has already been observed in the Adriatic Sea. These factors, combined with navigation, increase the possibility of spreading invasive alien species (IAS). Since IAS could have severe negative consequences on marine biodiversity and biosecurity, biota monitoring in ports is necessary. Ballast water, hull fouling and bilge water are the main ship compartments which must be controlled. Targeted IAS can be detected from these media by metabarcoding. Metabarcoding is the XXI century biological tool for rapid and effective species identification at all stages of its life history. It consists of the extraction of DNA (eDNA) from water or sediments and the identification of multiple species. Here we consider the possibility of early detection of IAS that could appear in the sea of Montenegro in the near future, using metabarcoding: algae *Rugulopteryx okamurae*, ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi*, barnacle *Austrominius modestus* and fish *Plotosus lineatus*. We will take samples from port Bar and port Kotor or/and marina Tivat. Recently discovered tubeworm *Ficopomatus enigmaticus* in Montenegro (in 2023) could have been detected by metabarcoding. According to Montenegrin laws, it is forbidden to bring non-native species into national waters with ballast and other waters, that is, it is mandatory to treat these waters adequately to prevent any form of sea pollution. Two of four species that could appear in the Montenegrin sea waters, presented here, are on the List of IAS of the Union concern of Regulation 1143/2014. Metabarcoding could serve as the most reliable early detection methodology for unwanted marine species and could accelerate and strengthen the capacity for monitoring, prevention, suppression and conservation law enforcement regarding marine IAS.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101079234 (BIOLAWEB project). The work was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Contract No: 451-03-66/2024-03/200026 and 451-03-66/2024-03/200039).

Keywords: ballast water, early detection, eDNA, marine invasive species, metabarcoding.

Alien zooplankton species in the port of Ploče and the Neretva estuary (south-eastern Adriatic Sea)

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Abstract

The port of Ploče, located at the mouth of the Neretva River, is one of the most important ports for international maritime traffic in the Adriatic. It therefore acts as a focal point for the introduction and further spread of alien species into nearby areas with potentially harmful consequences. Numerous alien species have already been detected in this water area. Zooplankton representatives include the ctenophora *Mnemiopsis leidyi*, the copepod *Pseudodiaptomus marinus* and the ciliate *Rhizodomus tagatzi*. Ctenophora *M. leidyi* was first observed in the port on September 12, 2017, and the estimated abundance was 1 ind.m⁻³. Only four days later, their numbers declined even further. They were observed again from early October to late November, with abundance varying from single individuals to smaller groups, depending on local hydrographic conditions. In September 2018, the species was observed again, but only for a few days and in lower densities. Only one month later, the alien copepod species *P. marinus* was detected for the first time in Ploče port and initially identified by DNA metabarcoding. Since 2021, individuals have been found in the plankton samples in the deeper saline layer of the Neretva up to Opuzen (16 km upstream of the estuary). The alien ciliate *R. tagatzi* was first detected in the port of Ploče on May 25, 2022 and only two months later reached a maximum abundance of $\sim 2 \times 10^3$ cells L⁻¹ in the seawater layer near Opuzen, which is one of the highest values in the Mediterranean and indicates a successful establishment of the population in the estuary and a strong influence on the functioning of the ecosystem. According to our findings, ballast water can be considered as the main transmission route for the mentioned zooplankton species in the Adriatic Sea. Although these species do not currently pose an obvious ecological problem in the port and estuary, they can displace native species and reduce biodiversity, especially in ecologically sensitive areas.

Keywords: non-indigenous species, ballast water, *Mnemiopsis leidyi*, *Pseudodiaptomus marinus*, *Rhizodomus tagatzi*

Understanding *Bursatella leachii* Blainville, 1817 in Croatian waters: molecular aspect of an alien marine species

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Abstract

The sea hare *Bursatella leachii* Blainville 1817 (Gastropoda; Aplysiidae) is a pantropical species but also abundant in the Mediterranean. Since its first record in the Mediterranean Sea in 1940 (Palestine), it has spread within the Mediterranean Sea. Its first record in Croatia was in 1986 (Rovinj, North Adriatic Sea). It was initially assumed that *B. leachii* originated from the Red Sea, but recent genetic approaches suggested that Mediterranean *B. leachii* may have an Atlantic rather than an Indo-Pacific origin. To explore this hypothesis, and preliminary assess the genetic diversity and structure of *B. leachii* population that inhabits Croatian waters, five specimens from two locations in the Middle Adriatic Sea (Split and Hvar) were collected and molecularly assessed. Mitochondrial DNA sequences were obtained, and analyses of phylogenetic tree and haplotype network were performed. Bayesian Inference and Maximum Likelihood were used to construct phylogenetic trees, for which 61 COI sequences of subclass Heterobranchia were used, combining GenBank records with sequences from this study. Both trees confirmed that Croatian *B. leachii* isolates belong to the same clade as other Mediterranean isolates. Moreover, the Haplotype Network of 53 *B. leachii* COI sequences from GenBank records revealed 15 haplotypes. Isolates from our study were part of two haplotypes named Hap_1 and Hap_2. While Hap_1 included only specimens from the Mediterranean, Hap_2 included Mediterranean and Western Atlantic specimens. Moreover, Hap_12 included Western Atlantic and Indo-Pacific specimens. Notably, there are no shared haplotypes between the Indo-Pacific and Mediterranean regions in our study. This finding supports previous research and the hypothesis that Mediterranean *B. leachii* have an Atlantic origin. This study highlights the need for molecular analyses to precisely determine the origins of species introduced into the Mediterranean.

Keywords: *Bursatella leachii*, marine alien species, phylogenetic tree, haplotype network

Managing Invasive Species with a Zero-Waste Approach: The Case of Spiny-Cheek Crayfish in Serbia

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Abstract

Invasive Alien Species (IAS) are among the top five direct drivers of biodiversity loss, posing a significant threat to humanity over the next decade. The spiny-cheek crayfish, *Faxonius limosus*, originally from Eastern North America, is now found in over 20 European countries and is listed as an IAS of Union concern. In Serbia, this species was first recorded in the Danube near Apatin in 2002 and has spread throughout the Serbian section of the Danube and its tributaries. Given its high dispersal rate, its actual invasive range in Serbia is likely broader than documented, with potential for further expansion. Spiny-cheek crayfish is a major aquatic invader in European inland waters, making its prevention, control, and eradication a significant challenge for biodiversity conservation. Effective management of invasive species involves innovative strategies that turn these challenges into a variety of eco-products, aligning with the ZERO WASTE concept. This research focuses on monitoring and trapping and reducing the crayfish population by transforming it into various industrially relevant eco-products, such as food and feed products, biosorbents, rubber bio-fillers, and bio-based packaging materials. Crayfish meat will be utilized to create innovative food, pet food, and feed products. The remaining shells, rich in chitin, the second most abundant polymer after cellulose, will be used to tackle two major environmental issues: aquatic ecosystem pollution by heavy metals and plastic pollution. Crayfish shells have excellent adsorption properties, making them effective for removing heavy metals from industrial effluents. However, managing saturated biosorbents remains a challenge. To address this, saturated biosorbents will be incinerated, and the resulting ash will be repurposed as a rubber bio-filler. Extracted chitin and proteins from shells will be used to produce bio-based packaging materials, providing an eco-friendly alternative to single-use plastics.

This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #GRANT No.7417. “Reducing the negative impact of invasive crayfish *F. limosus* in the Danube by smart exploitation of their meat and shells”, DANUBECare.

Keywords: Invasive species, spiny-cheek crayfish, zero waste, eco-products

T4: Fisheries resources and fishing technology

Status of relict species *Umbra krameri* Walbaum, 1792 in Serbian waters

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Abstract

The European mudminnow (*Umbra krameri* Walbaum, 1792) is the only autochthonous and relict species of the genus *Umbra* found in Europe and is endemic to the Danube and Dniester river basins. The species is bound to slow-flowing waters and shallow lakes with muddy bottom and rich vegetation, able to survive in water with low oxygen concentration. On the territory of Serbia, the umbra is strictly protected by the Rulebook on the Proclamation and Protection of Strictly Protected and Protected Wild Species of Plants, Animals and Fungi Annex I (“Official Gazette of RS”, No. 05/10). The Kraljevac Special Nature Reserve - SNR (Deliblatska peščara) is an area of floating and permanent islands that represent the remains of lowland wetlands, one of the world’s rarest and most endangered habitat types. It is characterized by a high degree of conservation of the biological features of the landscape and a high level of ecosystem and species diversity in a relatively small area. In December 2014, during the regular sampling of the ichthyofauna of Lake Kraljevac, a relict and endemic species of *Umbra krameri* was found. This is the third find in Serbia so far, in addition to the Special Nature Reserve “Zasavica” and the Kupusinački Danube-Tisa-Danube Canal. In December 2023, the detection of umbra was confirmed in a part of the Kraljevac watercourse. The specimens had a body length of 62 to 96 mm and a weight of 2.2 to 8.2 g and belonged to age classes 1⁺ to 3⁺. It can be said that the Kraljevac SNR is an area for preservation of the umbra population. Land reclamation works are destroying the habitats of the umbra, which is very sensitive to environmental changes caused by human disturbance of the habitat. In order to preserve the existing umbra population, it is necessary to develop a management plan.

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Keywords: umbra, records, protection, freshwater, Serbia

Integrating key ecosystem components into stock assessment models for fishery management

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Abstract

Climate change is leading to substantial environmental shifts worldwide, and hence to changes in ecosystem functioning, food webs and species distributions. Ecosystem-Based Fisheries Management (EBFM) initiatives have increased, in order to protect the ecological systems that support fisheries production. EBFM has led to more complex models for the assessment of fishery resources, capable of explaining and evaluating the relationships between the stock status and ecosystem components (e.g., changes in predator numbers and environmental variables such as sea surface temperature due to climate change). European anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) plays important roles in top-down and bottom-up control within the trophic network of the Adriatic Sea, and is economically important for this basin. Any variation in the biomass of this species would have ecological and economic consequences, leading to the need for close monitoring of this species for resource conservation. Currently, anchovy is assessed using age-structured population dynamics and surplus production models. These models present some limitations as they only consider biological information, survey estimates and data from fishery. It is critically important to develop stock assessments that take account of environmental and ecosystem variables. The integrated stock assessment platform, Stock Synthesis (SS3), will be applied with the aim of developing innovative models to assess the status of small pelagic fishery resources and evaluating the impact of key environmental drivers on these stocks. The analysis will examine whether regional environmental variables such as sea surface temperature (as proxy for reproduction triggers), chlorophyll concentration (as a proxy for food supply), river runoffs and salinity (as a proxy for population distribution) have statistically significant impacts on growth, recruitment and maturation, and hence population biomass.

Keywords: climate change, *Engraulis encrasicolus*, *Sardina pilchardus*, Adriatic Sea, Stock Synthesis, stock assessment, environmental variables, Ecosystem-based fisheries management

Could otolith shape tell us more? Adriatic sardine case

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Abstract

Sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*) is one of the most important pelagic fish species due to its huge ecological and economical role specially in the eastern side of Adriatic Sea. Sardine catches of around 47 thousand tonnes in the last ten years, make over 70% of the all Croatian landings. This species is shared stock between Adriatic countries and stock status is assessed on the entire GFCM GSA 17 and 18 area. Benchmark of the sardine, from 2023, indicated increased risk of overexploitation and overfishing, based on the biomass and catch levels. Age structure models were not successfully applied due mainly to the challenges in the age structure of the sardine stock. Namely, different interpretations of a number of the otolith rings resulted in differences in the age allocations and subsequently in the tracking of the cohorts. Therefore, additional effort is enforced on studying age, length and other aspects of the species morphology that could improve assessment models, to enable a more precautionary approach to protection of the species. Hence, from quartal samples of sardines collected within the DCF data framework otoliths were extracted (N=100), photographed and otolith shape indices with Fourier's analyses were calculated from images taken. Correlation of the total length (from 2.004 to 2.738mm) and total height (from 1.043 to 1.510mm) of otoliths, the shape indices of form factor (FF), roundness (RD), aspect ratio (AR), circularity (C), rectangularity (R) and ellipticity (E) with total fish length (from 11.6 to 16.2 cm) and weight (from 11.79 to 41.47 g) was tested showing different levels of relation. The results of this investigation could contribute to a better understanding of otolith morphometry and therefore easier age assignment.

Keywords: sardine, otolith shape, correlation

The establishment of the FRA (Fisheries Restricted Area) as a mechanism for the protection of bottom resources of the Adriatic

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Abstract

Demersal resources in the Adriatic Sea are in poor condition and most of the stocks are in a state of overfishing. Therefore, it is necessary to undertake urgent and restrictive fishing regulation measures in order to improve the situation and bring the intensity of exploitation in proportion to the state of resources. When establishing new measures, the specificities of demersal species of the Adriatic should be considered, which significantly complicates their application. These peculiarities are reflected in the fact that demersal fisheries in the Adriatic Sea are a typical multispecies fishery that takes place under conditions of multigear exploitation. Likewise, most stocks are short-lived organisms whose available biomass depends not only on the intensity of fishing effort but also on hydrographic conditions in the sea that affect recruitment. The situation is further complicated by the fact that most stocks are shared stock at the level of the Adriatic and are exploited by various national fleets of different fleet capacity and exploitation characteristics. Recently, various resource protection measures have been implemented in the countries of the Adriatic Sea, and the establishment of a Fisheries Restricted Area (FRA) in the Jabuka basin has proven to be the most efficient measure. The establishment of the FRA resulted in the significant recovery of stocks of most commercial species that inhabit this area, and the most positive changes were recorded in cartilaginous fish, hake and Norway lobster. This paper presents the changes in biomass, population structure and distribution of the most important species in Jabuka Pit after implementation of the FRA. Also, based on these successful results, the paper considers the needs and possibilities for the establishment of new protected areas in the Adriatic Sea.

Keywords: demersal resources, Adriatic Sea, fisheries regulations, FRA, Jabuka Pomo Pit

AdriaMed at 25th - Achievements, new challenges, and paving the way for future cooperation

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Abstract

The FAO AdriaMed Project is organizing an event on occasion of its 25th year of activity. The event will highlight the work done in the framework of the FAO AdriaMed Project and the broader efforts by countries towards the implementation of the FAO Code of Conduct for Fisheries for responsible fisheries and aquaculture in the Adriatic Sea. Panelists from the Adriatic countries will showcase experiences and lessons learnt with the final aim to stimulate discussion on how future efforts can ensure steps forward the achievements of the goals set by the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. In particular, the event has the following objectives: i) Shedding light on the most important achievements by the FAO AdriaMed Project with regards to fisheries and aquaculture research and management; ii) Showcasing the efforts and impact of research and programs, through discussions and success stories shared by panelists who were part of processes and activities implemented at national/international level; iii) Highlighting best practices and taking stock of what has been achieved to identify current gaps and/or opportunities and provide a vision for future development.

Keywords: international cooperation, shared stocks, fishery management, ecosystem approach to fisheries, aquaculture development, capacity development

Limits to commercial fishery in the 21st century

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Abstract

Due to its great success in technological development and corresponding increase over the centuries, today, commercial fishery is declining. Clearly, this is attributed to overfishing of fishes, molluscs, crustaceans and echinoderms. The conclusion follows from Klanjšček and Legović (2007), Legović (2008) and more recently from Lipej et al. (2022) who wrote: „All Adriatic fish stocks among those studied by Fernandes et al. (2017) were overexploited and depleted, as in the rest of the Mediterranean and Black Sea, Annual catches of fish and other sea organisms in the Adriatic Sea comprises about 15% of the total catch in the Mediterranean, which is disproportional to the surface area of the Adriatic Sea, which covers only 5.5% of the Mediterranean surface area. Since 1983, the quantity of fish caught is decreasing. It should be noted that the decline of the most vulnerable mega fauna (elasmobranchs and other large-sized fish species) commenced as early as the beginning of industrialisation of fisheries...” Hence, the key question is: Can commercial fishery survive, in the face of limited natural regeneration of the resources and economic limitations? By using mathematical models of single and multispecies fishery, it is concluded that in the future, current fishery management would cause further decrease in biodiversity of living organisms in the seas. Therefore, in the future, more extensive no-fishing zones are needed, further restrictions of fishing effort in commercial fishing zones need to be implemented and, at the same time, further incentives for development of aquaculture should be given by governments. These measures will require more intensive cross-border collaboration of marine scientists in order to estimate correct fishing effort for each fishing zone and commercial species.

Keywords: maximum sustainable yield, overfishing, single species fishery, multispecies fishery, Adriatic Sea

Marine recreational fishing in Italy and Albania. Critical issues and perspectives from national legislation

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Abstract

Beyond its important economic and social value, the activity of marine recreational fishing has a significant impact on fish stocks and affects professional fishing activities, particularly small-scale fishing, which is the most common type of commercial fishing in many countries, including Italy and Albania. The European Union has an exclusive competence in the area of the conservation of marine biological resources under the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP). In order to counter the risk of depletion of fish stocks, the Union has enacted a series of measures to regulate fishing opportunities and limit access to marine resources. Some of these measures have been adopted for recreational fishing. In addition, given the need for effective control of recreational fishing and an adequate system of sanctions in case of non-compliance with the rules of the CFP, the recent Regulation (EU) 2842/2023, which revises the control system of the CFP, has also intervened to reinforce the control system of recreational fisheries. This paper aims to analyze the Italian and Albanian legislation on recreational fishing, assessing critical issues and perspectives in the light of the CFP rules, aimed at the conservation and sustainable exploitation of marine biological resources, and in the light of the revision of the EU fisheries control system.

Keywords: Common Fisheries Policy, conservation of marine biological resources, fishing opportunities, control system

**Contribution to parasite fauna of Prespa Nase
(*Chondrostoma prespense* Karaman, 1924)
(Pisces: Cyprinidae) in lake Prespa, republic of N. Macedonia**

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Abstract

Eight out of the eleven indigenous fish species of Prespa are endemic, i.e. they exist only in Lake Prespa. One of these endemic fish species is Prespa nase (*Chondrostoma prespense*). The parasitological examination from the Macedonian part of the Lake Prespa in the period from 2022-2024 showed that 60 out of 72 examined specimens of Prespa nase were infested (83.33%). In our case study the presence of 13 parasite species was established: *Trichodina* sp., *Myxobolus exiguus*, *Gyrodactylus* sp., *Dactylogyrus elegantis*, *Dactylogyrus vistulae*, *Paradiplozoon zeller*, *Diplostomum spathaceum* (larva), *Tylodelphis clavata* (larva), *Bothriocephalus opsariichthydis*, *Raphidascaris acus* (larva) and *Ergasilus* sp., *Argulus foliaceus* and *Anodonta cygnea* (glochidia). Individually, by the parasite species, the highest prevalence was of *Myxobolus exiguus* and *Dactylogyrus vistulae* (found in 50,0% of Prespa nase each) while glochidia of *Anodonta cygnea* were found at 30,56% of fish and the lowest prevalence was with *Bothriocephalus opsariichthydis* and *Argulus foliaceus* (1,39% each), *Ergasilus* sp. and *Trichodina* sp. (2,78% each). In our case study the parasites *Gyrodactylus* sp. and *Myxobolus exiguus* are recorded for the first time in the ichthyoparasitofauna of Prespa nase of Lake Prespa and N. Macedonia.

We would like to thank for the grant support of PONT (Prespa Ohrid Nature Trust) for the project part “Understanding anthropogenic pressures on Lake Prespa”.

Keywords: Parasite fauna, *Chondrostoma prespense*, Lake Prespa

***Dentex maroccanus* in the southeastern Adriatic Sea?**

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Abstract

Genus *Dentex* are bony fish with prominent conical teeth, belonging to the family Sparidae. These species are considered commercially important, and are therefore valuable catch in the Mediterranean fisheries. It is commonly believed that three species belonging to the genus inhabit the Adriatic Sea, and those are: *Dentex dentex*, *D. gibbosus*, and *D. macrophthalmus*. However, recent research has identified the presence of an additional species, *D. maroccanus*, which is known to inhabit other areas of the Mediterranean Sea. Samples were obtained from the Montenegrin commercial trawling fleet, which operates in the southeastern Adriatic, mostly at a depth of up to 100 meters. Sampling started in November 2023 and has been continuously conducted since then, covering all seasons. Biological data from more than 1000 individuals have been collected, from both retained and discarded parts of the catch. Moreover, the number of gill rakers was counted on the first gill arch on more than 300 randomly selected individuals. Gill rakers are known as an important taxonomic marker for identifying both *D. maroccanus* and *D. macrophthalmus*. Additionally, samples were collected for DNA analysis to confirm these findings.

Keywords: dentex, Sparidae, Adriatic Sea, bottom trawl, demersal fishery

T5: Aquaculture and blue growth

Combining the Circular Economy and Blue Growth concepts to protect biodiversity and improve the sustainability of aquaculture: valorisation of sludge from wine processing wastes as a nutrient-rich fish feed ingredient

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Abstract

Given Greece's and Montenegro's significance of winery, as both are wine producers, and their interest on marine aquaculture, even having different scale of annual production, the investigation of locally available by-products aligns with sustainability goals and the effort to protect the biodiversity of both countries. The use of wineries wastes (wine sludge) as a raw material for fish feeds could play an important role contributing to the sustainable development of aquaculture, when its reuse is guided under the circular economy and blue growth concepts. The wine waste could be used to minimize the aquaculture impact while enhancing both the economical inputs of wineries and fish farms. The present study is part of a wider research which aims to understand its nutritional content and evaluate its potential as a raw material or functional fish feed additive. Due to the lack of this kind of research, there is a need for addressing the possible impacts into the farmed fish populations. To evaluate the wine sludge interaction with fish feed and the fish toxicity two different types of analysis were carried out. Chemical and toxicity tests used, which indicate the waste has a proper chemical composition for fish feeds and is not toxic for the farmed marine organisms. The results of chemical analysis of wine processing waste sludge shown protein content at 29.0%, carbohydrates at 47.0%, lipids at 0.6%, moisture at 9.5%, ash at 11.4%, crude fiber at 2.5%, indicating in total a nutrient-rich composition, essential for potential applications as a feed ingredient. These findings reveal that wine sludge exhibits a notable protein content of 29.0% and demonstrates non-toxicity to *Artemia* larvae, supporting the utilization of wine sludge, positioning it as a valuable asset for sustainable practices in the feed industry. However, more research is needed to test feeds prepared for fish with different nutritional needs.

Keywords: circular economy, blue growth, aquaculture, wine-sludge, reuse, wastes

Mussels and mussel farming in the wind of changes

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Abstract

Mussels are keystone species that perform numerous vital functions in the ecosystem, such as reef building, nutrient cycling, water quality improvement and biodiversity hotspots, and they are of great importance as seafood worldwide. These functions can be impaired by threats such as pollution, climate change, acidification and habitat destruction. In the Mediterranean, the important species *Mytilus galloprovincialis* is widely used as a sentinel organism for ecotoxicological studies (from classical pollutants to microplastics) and to study the effects of climate change, and is also of commercial importance for mussel farming. Due to the overexploitation of fishery resources, mariculture is developing into an important economic sector to compensate for the loss of fisheries. Mussel culture provides ecosystem services and is highly valued by consumers. Unfortunately, scientific research has shown that mussel farming is in decline and faces various problems such as disease, lack of spat, predation, HABs, pollution and low profitability. The recent survey on Slovenian mussel farming has revealed similar problems. The presentation will present the most important findings on *Mytilus galloprovincialis* in connection with threats and their significance for mussel farming with relevance for the Mediterranean region.

Keywords: *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, mussel farming, pollution, climate change, predation

Towards a regenerative Blue Economy: Mapping the Blue Economy

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Abstract

Blue Economy has various definitions, depending on the interpretation and principles discussed. There is no consensus on how to define it nor how to describe its founding principles. In this context, and as part of the France - International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Partnership 2021–2024 and with the support of the French Development Agency (AFD), IUCN conducted a mapping study defining three types of a Blue Economy from the perspective of conservation and sustainable development:

A Blue Economy rooted in the ‘maritime sector’, also known as ‘brown Blue Economy’, which includes the traditional activities of the ‘maritime sector’, which can be conflated with the ‘Ocean Economy’. It is clearly anthropocentric and based on a conventional and neoclassical economic model that operates as ‘business-as-usual’ (BAU).

A sustainable Blue Economy, striving to be more sustainable and inclusive, notably through the definition of a vision, definition, and guiding principles. However, debate still remains and much research abound to assess the economic, environmental, and societal performances of the sustainable Blue Economy.

The regenerative Blue Economy, emanating from a more profound pre-2012 claim by Pacific Island Countries, goes beyond mere economic factors: it is integrative, inclusive, and regenerative. It advocates for a new economic model able to meet global and local challenges. As it evolves, the definition of a regenerative Blue Economy progresses towards an economy that becomes an ‘actor’ in the fight against climate change and biodiversity loss, and contributes positively to such issues, thereby becoming an ‘Ocean-positive’ economy.

This presentation will showcase findings from this work, which is a first step in mapping the evolution of Blue Economy concepts, proposing a definition and founding principles for all Blue Economy-related work, through the lens of conservation and sustainable development, in all regions across the globe.

Keywords: Nature-based Solutions, regenerative blue economy, marine conservation, Sustainability

Cultivation potential of the macroalgae *Ulva compressa* at different nitrogen levels in aquaculture as an indicator of nitrogen absorption

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Abstract

Macroalgae are an important component of marine ecosystems, contributing to biomass production and playing a crucial role in ocean biogeochemistry. To successfully exploit cultivated *Ulva compressa*, its growth rate and yields need to be optimized. *Ulva compressa* is a macroalgae that is often found in coastal areas. It has been extensively studied for its ability to accumulate pollutants such as nitrogen and serve as a biomarker and remediate the environment. The aim of the present study was to investigate the growth performance, yield, survival rate and nutrient removal efficiency (NRE, %) of *Ulva compressa* in three different nitrogen-enriched growth media with different concentrations of Nitrogen contain into three different treatments (25N, 50N and 100N) over an experimental period of 35 days. Nine rectangular aquariums with a total volume of 10 L were filled with seawater with a salinity of 40 ppt. Temperature was adjusted at 22°C and photoperiod was 16 hours of light with LED illumination at an intensity of 12,500 LUX. In total, 45 gr biomass of *Ulva* was used, divided as 15 gr *Ulva* per treatment (5 gr/aquarium). Weekly measurements included the analysis of algae biomass and the determination of water parameters such as pH, temperature, ammonia (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻) and nitrite ions (NO₂⁻) using a spectrophotometric analysis. The results show significant differences in the growth performance and yield of *Ulva compressa* depending on the amount of NaNO₃ and indicate that the 100N concentration had the best biomass yield of 31.94±8.33 gr compared to treatments 25N and 50N. The 25N and 50N treatments showed a gradual increase in biomass until the 28th day, after this day growth slowed down, and the crop collapsed. In conclusion, macroalgae can be used as a means of improving water quality in intensive aquaculture, as they are considered good biomarkers that provide qualitative information on the level of nitrogen loading in the water.

Keywords: *Ulva compressa*, macroalgae growth, blue growth, aquaculture, nitrogen

The State of the Aquaculture and Freshwater Fisheries Sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina

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Abstract

The establishment of the first fish farm, the “Vrelo Bosne” farm, in Ilidža in 1894 marked the commencement of commercial aquaculture in Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H).

The modern freshwater aquaculture sector in B&H is mainly based on breeding salmonid (rainbow trout, brown trout, and brook trout) and cyprinid (carp, silver carp, and grass carp) species. Commercial, recreational, and sport fishing in freshwaters, as well as seawater fishing, are present in B&H’s fisheries industry. Of the entire freshwater ichthyofauna, about 50 species are important for sport fishing. Conversely, commercial fishing relies on a smaller range of species, with carp, catfish, perch, pike, bream, roach, silver carp, Danubian roach, etc. being the most economically significant.

Notwithstanding the tradition of aquaculture and fisheries and great potentials due to rich hydrological network and diverse ichthyofauna, the sector is largely underdeveloped and riddled with many challenges. Job-wise, the sector is still seen as an exclusively or predominantly male profession. The industry, and sport fishing in particular, is not prioritized, with no national fisheries policy in place, preventing the industry from receiving funding from both domestic and foreign sources.

The average consumption of fish meat in B&H was 5.8 kg per capita in 2017, compared to the European average of 21.5 kg. Still, the home market receives most of aquaculture production, with a small portion being exported to the European market (CEFTE, EFTE countries, etc.). However, in the era of Blue Growth, increasing export of fish and fish products to the demanding EU market could be an important strategic direction for B&H. A success will depend on meeting a number of requirements, such as adhering to all applicable legal requirements and food safety standards, as well as meeting all veterinary-hygienic and sanitary requirements (e.g., the HACCP standard) and any additional standards set forth by the manufacturer or exporter.

Keywords: aquaculture, fisheries, freshwater, Bosnia and Herzegovina

The maximum sustainable fish culture

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Abstract

According to FAO (2024) starting with 2022, aquaculture production has surpassed commercial fishery landings. However, given that mass mortality of fish in cages has already occurred repeatedly in the Philippines, Singapore, Norway and Canada, to mention a few, due to hypoxia or harmful algal blooms (HAB), the following question arises: What is the maximum sustainable biomass of fish in a fish farm? The key is to compute the maximum sustainable production of fish so that the resulting phytoplankton, which is fed by nutrients emanating from the fish farm, does not reach a concentration which will induce hypoxia subsequently. The maximum production of fish will depend on the natural limiting nutrient concentration, species of fish reared and quality of feed, nutrient inflow which is fuelling growth of the phytoplankton species that is most likely to develop intensive bloom and currents which disperse phytoplankton. The model developed by Legović and Cruzado, 1997 is upgraded to predict the maximum particulate limiting nutrient based on the above factors. Since the particulate nutrient is mainly found in the phytoplankton, a relationship is used to calculate the maximum phytoplankton concentration and hence the resulting subsequent hypoxia. In case of a possible occurrence of HAB, the resulting phytoplankton concentration needs to be lower than the concentration which will induce hypoxia. Given that the only control variable is the inflow of nutrients by the fish farm, the limit on the maximum sustainable biomass of fish and hence yearly production is obtained. Examples of calculation for the Bolinao Bay in the Philippines, Johor Strait (Singapore) and Red Sea will be shown. Finally, a potential for further development of aquaculture in the Adriatic Sea will be discussed. FAO, The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture, Rome, 2024. <https://www.fao.org/publications/home/fao-flagship-publications/the-state-of-world-fisheries-and-aquaculture>

Keywords: fish culture, limiting nutrient, phytoplankton bloom, hypoxia, HAB

Major cations in shell organic matrix of the Mediterranean mussel from the Adriatic coast of Montenegro

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Abstract

The content of major cations, namely sodium (Na), magnesium (Mg), potassium (K) and calcium (Ca), in four types of media, i.e., soft tissues, shells, and the products of shell demineralization (organic matrix - *conchix* and extract) of the Mediterranean mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* L., were determined. Mussels were sampled at three sites in the Boka Kotorska Bay of the Adriatic Sea: Sv. Nedjelja, Cogi and IMB. The main aim was to investigate the accumulation patterns of major cations in *conchix* and their possible relationship with other tested media. The highest content of Ca were found in shells and shell extracts, since their main constituent is calcium carbonate. Also, shell extracts had the highest concentration of Na due to EDTA disodium salt based solvent. Higher concentrations of Mg and K within the soft tissues in comparison to other media can be attributed to the roles of these minerals in mussel's physiological functions. PCA plot showed similarities in major cations accumulation in *conchixes* and shell extracts. According to CCA plot, shells are grouped around Ca, while soft tissues are in correlation with K and Mg. Moreover, shell extracts and *conchix* sample from Cogi are grouped around Na. Considering the relatively novel isolation procedure of intact organic matrix from shell, the accumulation patterns of major cations in *conchix*, soft tissues and shells could provide new insights in their distribution within the mussels and indicate possible relationships with trace metals that are important for the marine ecosystem assessment.

This paper was supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Innovation of Montenegro in the frame of bilateral project: AdriaOILplast (01-082/22-1678/1) between Montenegro and Slovenia 2023/24.

Keywords: major cations, shell organic matrix, Mediterranean mussel, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*

Aquatic Animal Health Surveillance in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Achievements, Status, and Challenges

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Abstract

In this manuscript, we present the achievements, current status, and challenges in Bosnia and Herzegovina's aquatic animal health 10 years after the implementation of the regional FAO project „Assistance to Western Balkan Countries for Improving Compliance to International Standards on Aquatic Animal Health”. The region has an advantageous situation with regard to fishery and aquaculture development, having large areas of high-quality waters, skilled labor and proximity to large markets in the European Union. To realize this potential, Western Balkan countries were seeking FAO assistance to develop the capacity to meet international standards for trade in live aquatic animals and their products. Primary among these were the standards of the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), the Agreement on the Application of Sanitary and Phyto-Sanitary Measures (SPS Agreement) of the World Trade Organization (WTO), and the standards for market access as required by the European Union (EU). The regional TCP proposal addressed the concerns expressed by the participating FAO member countries regarding the need to improve national and regional capacity for aquatic animal biosecurity. The proposal was built upon the results of an assessment of the status of national planning, policy and capacity for aquatic animal health in the five participating countries which enabled identifying the constraints to achieving national goals. The project assisted in strengthening regional and national aquatic biosecurity governance and capacities for dealing with transboundary aquatic animal diseases (TAADs), and in the process of improving compliance with international health standards for aquatic animals. Today, BiH is better able to maintain and improve national aquatic animal health status and comply with the health standard requirements of regional and international trading partners. However, challenges related to ongoing surveillance activities, antimicrobial usage and resistance and preparedness for emergency management of disasters, such as natural, technological and complex ones, should be further addressed by the cooperative action of competent authorities, producers, veterinary and aquatic services, and academia. An interdisciplinary approach to the aquatic sector, aligned with One Health principles, is the solution to deal with existing and emerging vulnerabilities of fishery and aquatic food systems.

Keywords: FAO, BiH, Aquatic animal health, surveillance, biosecurity, One health

Use of Adriatic Sea marine waste in biocomposites using bio-epoxy resin

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Abstract

The question of sea waste recycling, either as the refuse from the food system, such as it is the case for seashells (clams, mussels, oysters), or as a stranded material in overwhelming amounts, such as it is the case for *Posidonia oceanica*, appears crucial to substitute industrial materials for specific purposes, in a “circular economy” philosophy. In particular, dealing with composite materials, seashell powder can work as a mineral hardener, as biogenic calcium carbonate sources, while short *Posidonia* fibers can act to provide more tensile resistance to the composite. This work, which is part of the Seacomp project, funded by the Italian Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation Ministry (MAECI), has involved the use of these types of sea waste in amounts not exceeding 20%, as the fillers for both conventional epoxy (with petroleum-based phenols) and bio-epoxy (with bio-based phenols). Their potential application has been investigated by clarifying the criticalities of filler-matrix mixing, hence studying the mechanical performance of obtained samples by tensile and flexural testing, using both types of thermosetting resins. Finally, the characteristics of fracture for the composites have been compared with those obtained with conventional ceramic and cellulosic fillers. The tests have been carried out on samples as received and on samples conditioned by immersion into simulated seawater (35 g/l of sodium chloride solution) up to saturation, evaluating the different properties obtained. The outcome of this investigation would be clarifying the potential and the hindrances for scaling-up of these applications of sea waste, all coming from the Adriatic Sea, up to an industrial level, with the aim to maximize the amount of filler introduced with limited detriment for the performance of the composites.

Keywords: Biocomposites, seashells, *Posidonia oceanica*, sea waste recycling

Fish Collagen in the Function of Circular Economy

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Abstract

In recent years, the terms "sustainable development" and "circular economy" have become a mainstay in the green economy agenda. The need for environmentally friendly alternatives to the exploitation of natural resources dictated the approval of "Blue Growth", a long-term strategy aimed at sustainable growth in the maritime sector, by the European Commission. It is estimated that more than 50% of fish tissue, including scales, fins, heads, skin and viscera, is discarded as "waste", exceeding 20 million tons of by-products annually. The exploitation of marine by-products as a source of collagen is attracting the attention of researchers increasingly. Collagen extracted from fish scales is fat-, prion- and antibiotic-free, unlike collagen extracted from terrestrial animals, and as such represents a very interesting raw material for various industries and products, which fits into the circular economy model. An overview of the use of fish collagen in the production of medical textiles and textiles for wide use such as bionic polyester, bionic viscose and bionic polyamide is presented in this paper. Medical textiles in the form of collagen sponges and bandages stimulate cell adhesion and proliferation and contribute to wound healing. By adding collagen to the supramolecular structure of fibers, the properties of fibers and textile products can be changed. It has been shown that with the addition of collagen peptides, materials get a better hand feel, hydrophilicity, antistatic properties and better possibility for colourability.

Keywords: fish collagen, medical textiles, bionic fibers, circular economy

T6: Marine litter, ecotoxicology, and water pollution

Gill biomarkers for the effects of environmental pollution in *Blicca bjoerkna*

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Abstract

Due to their ability to accumulate pollutants, fish are often used as bioindicators of the status of aquatic ecosystems. The accumulation of pollutants generates high concentrations of free radicals that cause oxidative stress. White bream were collected from two sites at the Danube River that differ in their levels of pollutants, including heavy metals. Biomarkers of oxidative stress examined included the first line of defense antioxidant enzymes, superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT). In general, antioxidant enzymes were significantly higher in the gills of fish from the more contaminated site Višnjica than in fish samples from the reference site Veliko Ratno ostrvo. The measured SOD activity was 1.91 times higher and the CAT activity was even 4.5 times higher in fish from the reference site compared to the site under contamination. These data indicate that there are environmental stressors that lead to an increase in the concentration of superoxide anion radical and thus to an increase in SOD enzyme activity in the fish from the Višnjica site. The SOD enzyme converts the superoxide anion radical into hydrogen peroxide, which is then produced in excess, and consequently the activity of catalase, whose substrate it is, increases. Our results indicate that the white bream reacted differently depending on the environmental stress in each sampling area.

This research was funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia, contract No. 451-03-66/2024-03/200007.

Keywords: white bream, biomarker, pollution

Octopus fishing pots, a major plastic litter in the Thracian Sea, North Aegean Sea

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Abstract

Octopus fishing pots are the main fishing gear used for targeting the common octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*, Cuvier, 1797) in Greece. Although originally made of clay, during the 90s it was replaced in Europe, by plastic as a more durable, less heavy and less costly option. Since then, plastic octopus fishing pots (POFPs) started to become widespread, however the losses and the discard rates increased as the replacement by new ones is cheaper. The issue of abandoned POFPs is not local, or regional but global with POFPs from the Northwest coast of Africa reaching as far as the Caribbean and other coasts of the United States according to recent reports, while in other areas, e.g. the Atlantic coast of Spain research efforts manage to estimate the issue. The Thracian Sea is one of the most productive marine ecosystems in the Eastern Mediterranean and one of the major fishing grounds in Greece including the common octopus. This paper focuses on the issue of abandoned POFPs in the Thracian Sea. Between 2019 and 2023 and within the project Fishing for Litter, data has been collected in collaboration with 15 bottom trawlers who collect, record and report the waste that accumulates in their nets as part of their normal fishing activity. Based on data resulted from 65,274 hours of fishing activity, POFPs are among the most abundant litter items found in the area, with their percentage exceeding 57% of the total abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG) collected in the area. Given the results we draw suggestions for tackling the issue, which include increase patrolling, altering the material from PP or PVC to HDPE so they can be recycled when retrieved from the sea, redescribing the fishing tool “plastic octopus pots” in the legislation with more details and requirements and last subsidise fishers to replace POFPs with paddles in order to continue fishing the common octopus but with far less wastes.

Keywords: ALDFG, marine pollution, eastern Mediterranean, fisheries management

Tackling plastic pollution in the Mediterranean Sea

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Abstract

The Mediterranean Sea, a vital and biodiverse region, is grappling with extensive plastic pollution, estimated at 1,178,000 tonnes, significantly affecting its marine ecosystems, food supplies, and coastal economies. The “Plastic Waste Free Islands Mediterranean” project, part of the global “Close the plastic tap” IUCN programme, coordinated by the IUCN Centre for Mediterranean Cooperation and funded by the Didier and Martine Primat Foundation, was initiated to address this challenge. Spanning from January 2019 to April 2022, the project focused on the islands of Menorca and Cyprus, aiming to demonstrate effective, quantifiable solutions to plastic leakage. At present part of the model is being tested in Tunisia and Albania. The project employed methodologies to identify and prioritize areas with the highest plastic leakage, providing a strong evidence base for policy-making and targeted interventions, increasing effectiveness of policies aimed at reducing plastic waste. Thanks to the actions developed we were able to enhance the understanding of plastic waste generation, explore circular economy models to transform plastic waste into new products, and to demonstrate potential financial, environmental, and social benefits, including lower waste disposal costs, reduced landfill pressure, job creation, and decreased carbon emissions. The project emphasized collaboration with local governments, businesses, and communities, ensuring the sustainability and scalability of the initiatives to encourage the targeted sectors to adopt plastic leakage reduction measures. The project’s success demonstrated that concerted effort, innovative solutions, broad stakeholder engagement and holistic, collaborative approaches can significantly support the reduction of plastic leakage and pollution in the Mediterranean.

Keywords: plastic pollution, Mediterranean Sea, waste management, circular economy, stakeholder engagement

Evaluation of the impact of Commercial port activity in the environmental situation of Vlora bay, Albania

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Abstract

In recent years, maritime transport has seen a significant rise, leading to a reduction in global transport. Vlora Bay is one of the most attractive coastal zones of Albania, and it presents suitable conditions to accommodate various types of vessels and ships. The Commercial port of Vlora is one of the main ports in the South of Albania, serving for the transport of goods and passengers. The water quality in this area is affected by a variety of potential pollutant sources, including boat and ship antifouling agents, boat hull cleaning, and other releases and discharges from boats, wastewater discharges from municipalities and industrial facilities, etc. Water exchange in bays is often limited and shipping activities introduce several contaminants (oil, trace metals, nutrients and organochlorine compounds). This study focuses on seawater quality of Vlora Bay and the evaluation of the impact of commercial port activity in the environmental situation of this bay. The seawater quality survey was performed by determine some physical-chemical parameters such as temperature, pH, conductivity (mS/cm), (DO), biological oxygen demand (BOD), total solid soils (TSS), total dissolved soils (TDS) and nutrients (N/NO₂⁻, N/NO₃⁻, P/PO₄³⁻,). Water samples were collected from the network of ten sampling points as following: five samples in the Commercial port of Vlora; five samples along Vlora bay. One of the water samples was collected far from the port (500 m from the shore, near Orikum) and was used as a comparative sample. The results showed a higher content of nutrients in sea water samples collected in the port and Vlora Bay (in the area around port) compared to their content in the water sample collected in a considerable distance from the port. But referred to Seawater Quality Standards, the water quality in Vlora Bay resulted quite good.

Keywords: Vlora bay, port, sea water quality, physical-chemical parameters, nutrients.

Application of smart sensors and national pollution hub for preventing marine water pollution in Albania

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Abstract

The importance of marine water monitoring in mitigating marine incidents lies in its ability to quickly detect and prevent problems such as oil spills, waste dumping, thermal pollution, harmful algal blooms, etc. This paper describes different aspects of the development of an early warning system for preventing and mitigating marine pollution in the Mediterranean Sea. The countries involved in this project called SEAVIEWS were: Greece, Albania, Croatia, Italy, Montenegro and Slovenia. This cooperation was achieved through the development of a transnational repository network (smart sensors installed in critical coastal areas, web platform, servers, mobile application, marine pollution hubs). This network is able to receive, store and analyse the seawater quality data by using smart sensor probes installed in critical points of Adriatic-Ionian Sea. Two multi-parametric probes with smart sensors were installed in Vlora Bay and Durrësi Bay in Albania. The probes held the sensors for temperature, conductivity, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), turbidity, and depth. Other parameters, such as salinity, total dissolved solids (TDS), and oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), were calculated through built-in correlations. The web platform can transmit alert messages to the governmental bodies responsible for marine incidents. The transnational repository network receives also information from public observations through mobile application developed for this purpose. The goal of this mobile application is to promote through the network the people's understanding and sensitivity and therefore, engage them in the prevention of marine pollution. The composition and the strategic plan for the operation of Albanian National Pollution Hub will be described here. Through the creation of an open community supported by the marine hubs, we expect to raise awareness on marine pollution, ensure exploitation activities, identify new relevant stakeholders and in the long-term achieve contributions to the amendment of current policies applied in the Mediterranean area.

Keywords: marine pollution, Albania, water parameters, sensor, Mediterranean Sea

Rivers in Montenegro which belong to the Adriatic Basin as secondary sources of microplastics along the Montenegrin coast

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Abstract

Rivers are considered one of the main sources of microplastics (MP) into the seas and oceans and the main transport vector of plastic waste from terrestrial sources, so the study of MP in rivers is of great importance. In the present study, we investigated microplastics pollution in inshore surface sediments of selected rivers in Montenegro which belong to the Adriatic Basin. Microplastics were identified in all studied rivers (Zeta, Morača and Bojana) sediment samples with an average abundance, in the three rivers combined, of 163.6 ± 96.1 MPs/kg of dry sediment. The sediment of the selected rivers in Montenegro which belong to the Adriatic Basin are moderately to highly polluted with microplastics, depending on the examined location and seasons of sampling, compared with other studies. The most common shape of microplastics were filaments and fragments. Polypropylene and polyethylene were the most commonly identified polymers in all sediment samples. This study indicated that the inflow of freshwater ecosystems from the Adriatic basin of Montenegro in this study contributes to the increased MP amount on the Montenegrin coast. The results of this study have a great potential to influence the behavior of the population and local communities in order to reduce the use of single-use plastic products, improve waste and wastewater management, as well as in creating solutions and rehabilitation measures. This study provides a baseline for further investigations and monitoring of MPs

Keywords: microplastics, sediment, rivers, Adriatic Basin, Montenegrin coast

Comparative advantages of the rapid method for methylmercury determination in seafood using direct mercury analyzer

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Abstract

Methylmercury (MeHg), the prevalent form of mercury (Hg) in seafood, is also the most harmful for humans, causing various adverse effects depending on the duration, frequency, and susceptibility of exposure. Microorganisms convert elemental Hg in water into MeHg, which enters animal bodies and which concentrations are magnified through the food chain. The widespread presence of MeHg and the strict limits regarding its maximum concentrations in seafood set by state, regional, and world institutions and organizations emphasize the importance of accurately and efficiently determining MeHg concentrations. This paper aims to draw the attention of interested parties to the rapid method for MeHg determination in seafood using Direct Mercury Analyzer (DMA) and to emphasize its comparative advantages over other conventional analytical techniques. The MeHg determination is frequently performed by coupling Gas Chromatography (GC) or High-Performance Liquid chromatography (HPLC) to different detectors such as Electron Impact - Mass Spectrometry (EI-MS), Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS), Microwave Induced Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectrometry (MIP-AES), Cold Vapor-Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (CV-AAS) and Cold Vapor-Atomic Fluorescence Spectrometry (CV-AFS). On the other hand, one of the most effective techniques used today encompasses sample extraction (combining hydrochloric acid, toluene, and sodium thiosulfate) and the use of DMA. The advantages over other typically used methods include ease of use (after a simple extraction procedure, stabilized samples are inserted into the automatic sampler and analyzed by DMA), extremely low detection limit (as low as 0.0015 ng), matrix-independent results (applicable for both solid and aqueous, organic and inorganic samples), low running cost (saves up to 70%), and achieving high accuracy and reproducibility (confirmed by the analysis of standard reference materials) along with high productivity.

This work was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (grant no 451-03-66/2024-03/200017).

Keywords: methylmercury, rapid determination, extraction, Direct Mercury Analyzer

First record of methylmercury concentrations in mussels and oysters from Boka Kotorska Bay

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Abstract

Environmental conditions in Boka Kotorska Bay are favorable for the industrial development of the mariculture sector, especially for shellfish growing. Currently, two edible bivalve species are being cultivated: mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) and oysters (*Ostrea edulis*), and the natural potential of the area appears promising for the future development of Montenegrin aquaculture. Along with other toxic metals, measuring and monitoring the methylmercury (MeHg) levels in cultivated bivalve species is crucial, given that this form of mercury (Hg) is a significant environmental pollution and health issue. The results of this study present the first experimental data for MeHg content in both species from this part of the Adriatic Sea. Samples were collected at the mussel and oyster farm at the location Ljuta (geographical coordinates: I. 42°28'32.13"N 18°45'51.16"E, II. 42°28'28.33"N 18°45'50.70"E, III. 42°28'50"N 18°45'47.20"E, IV. 42°28'32.03"N 18°45'47.81"E). After lyophilization, pulverization, and homogenization of the samples, the separation of MeHg was performed (three replicates) by a two-step extraction procedure (organic extraction and back-extraction to the aqueous medium), and the MeHg concentrations were measured using a Direct Mercury Analyzer (DMA-80, Milestone). The coefficient of determination of the calibration curve was 0.9998, LOD=0.031 ppb, and LOQ=0.093 ppb. The accuracy of the applied procedure was verified using SRM 2976 (mussel tissue) and SRM 1566b (oyster tissue), with MeHg recovery rates of 101.5% and 103.2%. The concentrations of MeHg in the soft tissues of mussels and oysters were 0.0236±0.0007 mg/kg and 0.0201±0.0009 mg/kg dry weight. This corresponds to 0.0041±0.0001 mg/kg and 0.0037±0.0002 mg/kg wet weight for mussels and oysters. The measured MeHg concentrations were significantly lower than the provisional restriction of 0.3 mg/kg ww prescribed by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), indicating safety for consuming.

Keywords: methylmercury, bivalves, mariculture, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Ostrea edulis*, Boka Kotorska Bay

Combatting Sea Turtle By catch: Addressing Ghost Gear in Drini Bay

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Abstract

The estimated 640.000 tons of fishing gear lost, abandoned, or discarded annually exerts a large but uncertain impact on marine species. According to research colleagues, partner organizations, fishers and sea turtle recovery centers, ghost loglines, illegal driftnets and FADs are the number one cause of mortality for sea turtles in the Western Mediterranean Sea. (Save the Med Foundation, August 2020). Ghost fishing is a severe threat for all seven species of sea turtles found worldwide. Many turtles become entangled when they use the ghost net mats as shelter and as a food source. For sea turtles, entanglement can cause exhaustion, dehydration, decreased swimming ability, reduced feeding, life-threatening injuries, and eventually death. The purpose of this study is to determine the positions of ghost gear in Drini bay, and then their removal where possible. To achieve this goal, 3 modules have been developed: (1) underwater survey, (2) removal of ghost gears located and (3) raising fishermen's awareness. A 39.8 % reduction in the amount of ghost gears in Drini Bay has caused 24.1 % of turtles to be saved from getting stuck in lost nets. And 13.8 % of fishermen are aware of the impact of ghost gear on marine life, impacting also their own business. Based on the results, the effect that ghost gears have on sea turtles populations is obvious. It is almost impossible to remove all the ghost gears from the seabed, but we can focus on awareness campaigns which have a very positive effect on fishermen, showing the very harmful effects of ghost gears on marine life, the sense of responsibility has been strengthened among fishermen to eliminate the intentional throwing of damaged nets into the sea.

Keywords: turtle, fisherman, ghost gear, underwater survey

Assessment of marine litter on Montenegrin beaches (south Adriatic Sea)

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Abstract

Analyses of the amount, distribution and categorization of beach litter were conducted in winter and spring season 2023 on three beaches along the Montenegrin coast (Blatna beach, Jaz beach and Velika beach), in line with UNEP/MAP 'Adopt a beach' guidelines. In total, 1788 items/100m with total weight of 173.09 kg were collected during two seasons. In the winter season, 1078 items/100m of beach stretch with a total weight of 110.48 kg and the average litter density of 0.089 items/m² were collected. In the spring season, 710 items/100m with a total weight of 62.61 kg and the average litter density of 0.054 items/m² were collected. In both surveys, the artificial polymer materials prevailed in abundance – 73.45% and 66.05%, respectively. The dominant categories were: plastic/polystyrene pieces from 2.5 cm to 50 cm, drink bottles, plastic caps and lids (including rings from bottle caps/lids), other plastic/polystyrene items (identifiable) including fragments and other wood material (< 50 cm). The Clean Coast Index (CCI) was calculated to classify beaches in five categories for evaluating the cleanliness level of the coast observed at each survey. All beaches belonged to two categories: "Very Clean" (winter and spring surveys) and "Clean" (winter surveys). The results were compared with baseline and threshold values, (UNEP/MED WG.482/23), and indicated that the pollution on Montenegrin beaches was above the recommended values for winter season only on Blatna beach (136.69 items/m²) and under the recommended values for spring season on the all three beaches (59.67 items/m² on Blatna beach, 60.29 items/m² on Jaz beach and 46.06 items/m² on Velika beach). Results from nonparametric Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis tests showed that items abundance among locations did not differ significantly ($Z=1.74$, $p>0.05$), as well as among seasons ($H=0.28$, $p>0.05$).

Keywords: marine litter composition, beach monitoring, pollution, South Adriatic Sea

Improving sediment quality in Blue Flag marinas over 15 years

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Abstract

In the study on the abundance of elements in the sediments of the eastern Adriatic Sea, conducted from 2005 to 2010, we have found that the sediments in marinas have elevated levels of Cu, Zn, As and Pb due to leaching or washing of antifouling paints from boat hulls. The highest concentrations were found in the service areas of marinas where boats are repaired and washed. This is because it was common practice in most marinas to remove old antifouling paints by washing them directly into the sea. As part of the environmental protection measures, that should be implemented in marinas to reduce harmful pollutants in the water column and sediments, it was proposed to install wastewater treatment plants to remove oil and heavy metals from the wastewater collected in the marinas' service areas. This has been implemented within the "Blue Flag for Marinas" program, in which marinas participate voluntarily and are awarded the Blue Flag if they meet a number of safety, environmental and sustainability criteria, including the criterion that no contaminants are allowed to enter the sea or sewage system. To investigate the effectiveness of the environmental protection measures implemented under the Blue Flag program, we re-examined the sediments from 14 Croatian Blue Flag marinas to assess trends in Cu, Zn, As and Pb concentrations 15 years after the first study. Sediments were taken from the same locations and analyses were carried out in the same way in both studies using tube-excited energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence. The results showed an improvement in sediment quality in about 50% of the marinas studied due to the installation of wastewater treatment plants. A further 20% maintained good sediment quality, while 30% have shown deterioration in sediment quality despite installing wastewater treatment plants. Although the majority of marinas studied have managed to maintain or reduce sediment pollution, the study shows that continuous monitoring and possibly stricter management strategies are needed to ensure a sustainable reduction of pollutants in the Adriatic.

Keywords: Adriatic marinas, heavy metals, blue Flag, sediment pollution, environmental protection

Trace elements in *Sardina pilchardus* from Montenegrin coast - human health risk assessment

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Abstract

Seafood and fish are major sources of human exposure to trace elements. As global fish consumption rises, assessing trace element levels and associated health risks is essential. This study examined trace elements (As, Hg, Pb, Cd, Cu, Fe, Mn, Zn) in *Sardina pilchardus* from Boka Kotorska Bay and coastal part of the Montenegrin open sea, alongside related human health risks assessment. Fish samples were homogenized and digested with HNO₃ and H₂O₂ in a microwave digestion system. Pb and Cd concentrations were measured by graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry, and the remaining elements, except Hg, by inductively coupled plasma – optical emission spectrometry. Hg content was measured directly using an advanced mercury analyzer. The health risk was assessed using the target hazard quotient (THQ), comparing trace element exposure to reference doses. The results showed that Fe and Zn were the most abundant, followed by As, Mn, and Cu, with Hg, Pb, and Cd present in lowest concentrations. However, the highest THQ values were found for Hg, although all obtained values remained below 1, indicating no immediate risk. Nonetheless, due to Hg's widespread presence, its ability to bioaccumulate, and its serious toxic effects, including neurotoxicity, particularly in children, these findings warrant caution. The cumulative effect of Hg from various dietary sources and diverse fish consumption patterns highlight the need for more detailed studies. Specifically, the human population is primarily exposed to methyl Hg, the most toxic form of Hg, through the consumption of fish and seafood products. Certain benthic, demersal, and large predatory fish species contain considerably higher Hg levels than *S. pilchardus*. Future research should focus on Hg speciation analysis and fish-specific consumption rates to ensure a comprehensive assessment of human exposure to trace elements through fish consumption.

This work has been supported by the Ministry of Science of Montenegro, Bilateral project between Montenegro and Serbia, ECOFISH (contract no. 01-3439).

Keywords: trace elements, fish, human health, Montenegrin coast

Estimation of biological and chemical parameters in Kumbor area (Boka Kotorska Bay)

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Abstract

This research assesses the quality and trophic status of the marine environment in the Porto Novi area (Bokakotorska Bay) focusing on the spatial and seasonal distribution of physicochemical parameters, bacteria, and phytoplankton parameters. It is also important to identify the relative contributions of environmental variables as possible factors influencing the distribution of microorganisms. Despite efforts to include more locations in monitoring in Montenegro, this part of the Kumbor area was not studied years ago. With the construction of a luxury marina and settlement, this coastal zone is becoming increasingly important. The variations between the investigated variables were statistically more pronounced in the different seasons than at the individual stations. Temperature seems to be the main factor for the fluctuation in bacteria and phytoplankton in seawater. According to the National Legislation of Montenegro, the study's results of nutrients and bacteria mainly meet the prescribed criteria except for nitrite concentration in the winter season at the PN3 station. The highest number of fecal bacteria was recorded in the spring season at the PN1 station. The harmful species, which are potential producers of toxins, did not show high concentrations. However, the microplankton community reached 10^5 cells/L and the *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. reached 10^4 cells/L indicating characteristics of mesotrophic area. The PCA analysis separated PN1 (station under the greater impact of fresh water), PN2 (marina station), and PN3 (entrance to the marina). These stations might be the subject of future monitoring assessments employing molecular methods.

The investigation was conducted within the project “Monitoring of marine ecosystem in part of the marina Porto Novi, in Kumbor, Herceg Novi” with cooperation Doo Azmont Investment.

Keywords: pollution, Bokakotorska Bay, bacteria, nutrients, phytoplankton

Polyethylene microplastics as vector for tributyltin (TBT) transfer in mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*

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Abstract

Tributyltin (TBT) is known to be a potent pollutant to biota and the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) has banned the use of TBT in antifouling paints. Due to the new inputs of TBT reported worldwide, this pollutant cannot be neglected. Given the ubiquitous presence of microplastics in the environment and the persistence of TBT together with new hot spots, there is concern that TBT adsorbed to microplastics through hydrophobic interactions could pose a risk to marine ecosystems via adverse effects on biota. Mussels serve as sentinel organisms in environmental studies, they are important engineering species in the marine environment and also important in mussel cultures worldwide. Exposure to TBT chloride is known to disrupt metabolic pathways in oysters, affecting homeostasis, mitochondrial metabolism and antioxidant response, increasing mortality and impairing gamete formation, which can lead to population declines in polluted areas. The aim of our study was to determine whether microplastics act as a vector for the transfer of TBT into bivalves and whether this input leads to greater adverse effects compared to input of TBT dissolved in seawater. We assessed the effects of this combination on potential metabolic activity via idonitrotetrazolium chloride reduction capacity and genotoxicity using the Comet assay.

Keywords: tributyltin chloride, polyethylene microplastics, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*

T7: Marine protected areas, conservation of aquatic resources and ecosystems

Engaging fishers in sea turtle conservation in the Mediterranean Sea

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Abstract

In the Mediterranean Sea, more than 121,000 sea turtles are incidentally caught each year by a variety of fishing gears, with more than 33,000 deaths and a mortality rate ranging from 10 to 50% depending on the type of fishing gear. Defining how to engage the fishers who are directly involved in incidental catches of turtles is critical to raise their interest, increase awareness and foster their collaboration with the scientific community and authorities. We developed a conceptual model to define the objectives of sea turtle conservation (Final Targets, FTs) at a management, technical, educational, and social level. The achievement of FTs was assessed through four Indicators (interest, scepticism, awareness, cooperation) based on the perception and behaviour of fishers. A 3-phase roadmap was set to engage fishers: 1) Meeting, it is the initial contact between the scientific community and the fishers to create baseline information on where, when, and how bycatch occurs; 2) Deepening the knowledge, it mainly consists on trainings to increase fishers' awareness of good practices and sustainable fisheries; 3) In the field, where scientists and fishers test innovative bycatch reduction devices (BRDs) aboard on commercial fishing vessel to comprehend the perspective of fishers in terms of the technical solutions proposed by scientists. Combining a theoretical and an empirical approach, this study provides successful indications (bycatch hot-spots, technological innovation of fishing gear, communication strategies, eco-labelling, improved sea turtle survivability) on how to achieve large-scale sea turtle conservation, which could be replicated in other areas.

Keywords: Biodiversity conservation, Fishers' engagement, Sea turtles, Sustainable fishery, Mediterranean Sea

The French Biodiversity Agency's (FBA) engagement for ecosystem conservation in Adriatic Sea: from endangered species to sustainable management tools and education

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Abstract

The French Biodiversity Agency (FBA) is dedicated to the conservation of ecosystems in the Mediterranean Sea and the Caribbeans and would like to propose several actions that could be undertaken in the Adriatic Sea, with a particular focus on endangered species and sustainable management tools. We are committed to the development and enforcement of regulations protecting *Posidonia* meadows. This includes implementing legislation against anchoring on these meadows and supporting departments responsible for regulating anchoring of large vessels in France. In terms of management measures, we aim to simplify administrative procedures for eco-mooring installations, protect *Posidonia* banks, encourage stakeholders to sign the Act4Posidonia charter, and propose sustainable fishing techniques. We also promote the implementation of the ERC approach (avoid, reduce, compensate) for all development projects and foster the creation of Alliance Posidonia FRANCE, a network of public and private entities committed to *Posidonia* protection. Additionally, FBA is active in educational initiatives such as “aires éducatives,” projects where students collectively engage in the preservation of local territories. These projects reconnect students with nature, cultivate eco-citizenship, and integrate experiential learning with theoretical knowledge, encouraging active public involvement from a young age. Furthermore, FBA works on marine mammal protection through the Agorà Sanctuary. This management plan includes eight strategic axes and 25 operational measures encompassing 80 management actions and 141 specific activities. These actions aim to improve knowledge on cetacean hunting impacts in the Caribbean, assess and mitigate collisions, document and address pollution sources, evaluate acoustic pollution impacts, and foster sustainable practices in whale watching. We also aim to strengthen research collaborations, enhance knowledge dissemination internationally, and bolster Caribbean cooperation efforts.

Keywords: *Posidonia*, mammal protection, educative tool

Genetic adaptation of *Pinna nobilis* to the parasite *Haplosporidium pinnae*

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Abstract

In less than a decade, the endemic Mediterranean mussel, *Pinna nobilis*, has experienced several mass mortality events (MME) across the Mediterranean Sea, due to opportunistic pathogens, including the parasite *Haplosporidium pinnae*. Today, the species almost disappeared in the open Sea. Hopefully, few lagoons still support healthy populations, even if they are not spared from parasitic exposure, and some individuals were found resistant to one or more parasite-induced MME, suggesting that the species has a potential to survive. In a recent study focusing on the description of the diversity of Toll-like receptors (TLR) in *P. nobilis*, we demonstrated that most individuals identified as resistant to *H. pinnae*, and only those, were introgressed by the genome of *P. rudis*, at the TLR-7 locus. Thus, resistance may likely rely on a set of genes of *P. rudis* origin, consistent with the observation that *P. nobilis* x *P. rudis* hybrids are indeed naturally resistant to the parasite. Analysis of the entire genome sequences suggests that all of our *P. nobilis* genomes actually contain on average 1% of the *P. rudis* genome, revealing that hybridization between the two species has often occurred in the past. Here we present our updated results regarding the set of introgressed genes likely involved in the resistance to *H. pinnae* and discuss the perspectives of these findings for the conservation of the species.

Keywords: Fan mussel, *Pinna nobilis*, *Pinna rudis*, *Haplosporidium pinnae*, genetic monitoring, genetic adaptation, genetic diversity, species conservation, genomic studies

Population status of the critically endangered fan mussel (*Pinna nobilis*) in French coastal lagoons

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Abstract

Since 2016, the emblematic and critically endangered bivalve *Pinna nobilis* has been suffering from mass mortality events (MMEs) mainly due to the pathogen *Haplosporidium pinnae*. All known populations in the open sea have been decimated, leaving coastal lagoons as the last sanctuaries for the species. This study evaluates the status of *P. nobilis* populations in four coastal lagoons. Thau Lagoon: As of January 2024, 1931 live *P. nobilis* were recorded across 30 surveyed sites. The population exhibits a range of size classes from recruits to adults, with densities up to 25 individuals per 100 m². Despite a localized MME in 2020, new recruits in previously affected areas suggest population recovery and resilience. Thau Lagoon thus represents a critical sanctuary for *P. nobilis*. Urbinu Lagoon: Last surveys in May 2024 identified 24 live individuals. The dense *Cymodocea nodosa* seagrass meadow may impede recruitment, and sporadic connection to the open sea limits larval entry. However, the observation of juveniles indicates some recruitment, though the population remains small and vulnerable. Diana Lagoon: The majority of the population resides in *Cymodocea nodosa* seagrass meadows in shallow southern waters. In May 2024, approximately 25% of the 286 individuals settled in the southern part were dead, indicating a significant recent mortality event. Grazel Lagoon: Surveys in 2023 recorded 73 live individuals in shallow waters (0.5 to 1.5 m depth), with varying habitats including *Zostera noltei* seagrass. The lagoon's salinity is similar to the open sea, potentially allowing the study of resistant individuals. These lagoons serve as the last refuges for *P. nobilis*, highlighting their critical role in the conservation of this endangered species. Further monitoring and protective measures are essential to ensure their survival.

Keywords: fan mussel, *Pinna nobilis*, epizootic, coastal lagoon, conservation, Mediterranean

Population Status and Conservation of the Critically Endangered Fan Mussel (*Pinna nobilis*) in Thau Lagoon, France

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Abstract

Since 2016, the noble pen shell (*Pinna nobilis*), a giant bivalve endemic to the Mediterranean Sea, has faced mass mortality events (MMEs) mainly due to the pathogen *Haplosporidium pinnae*. These events have nearly eradicated all known populations in open seas, making coastal lagoons the last refuges for this critically endangered species. This study focuses on the population status of *P. nobilis* in Thau Lagoon (France), one of the very last sanctuaries at the Mediterranean scale. Censuses carried out between July 2022 and January 2024 recorded 1,931 live *P. nobilis* individuals across 30 surveyed sites. These individuals exhibited various size-class distributions, indicating recruitment and a range from young recruits to mature adults. High-density populations, with up to 25 individuals per 100 m², were found in specific areas. The species was observed from the lagoon's edges to its central deeper zones up to 9 meters deep. Despite a localized MME in late 2020 due to *H. pinnae*, signs of population recovery and resilience were observed, with new individuals appearing in previously infected areas. This indicates a potential for natural resistance and adaptation. The lagoon's unique environmental conditions may contribute to limiting pathogen spread, making it a critical sanctuary for *P. nobilis* conservation. The study highlights the importance of Thau Lagoon in preserving *P. nobilis*. The lagoon's population appears robust, with indications of ongoing recruitment and survival across various habitats. Given the critical situation of *P. nobilis* in the Mediterranean, targeted conservation actions are imperative. The findings of this study should drive urgent efforts to protect and sustain the lagoon's *P. nobilis* populations, leveraging their resilience to support broader repopulation initiatives in the Mediterranean Sea.

Keywords: Fan mussel, *Pinna nobilis*, epizootic, coastal lagoon, conservation, Mediterranean, bivalvia

The Green Secret of the Adriatic Sea: New Approaches to Utilize *Ulva spp.* from Boka Kotorska Bay

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Abstract

The seas have become attractive alternatives for exploiting valuable nutrient resources. Macroalgae, commonly known as seaweeds, are probably the future functional food or pharmaceuticals since they have been recognized as multi-food use sea crops, with many nutritional and health benefits. The *Ulva spp.* are among the most widespread edible seaweeds, rich with polyphenolics and natural pigments, but not sufficiently exploited due to the specific taste and sensitivity of these bioactive compounds. The focus of this research was to establish new ways of utilizing *Ulva*, by applying green and safe innovative technologies for extracting and preserving bioactive compounds, making *Ulva* more acceptable for food or pharmaceutical consumption. The sampling of *Ulva spp.* in Boka Kotorska Bay (Adriatic Sea) was performed in July 2023 (Institute of Marine Biology, Kotor, Montenegro). The dried samples were prepared for extraction, before the microencapsulation process. Optimal extract, rich with bioactive compounds was produced by the principles of green chemistry, using ethanol-water as a solvent, by the traditional extraction method, maceration. Innovative microencapsulation approaches were performed for the preservation of *Ulva*-extracted bio-compounds (spray and freeze-drying techniques). The obtained microencapsulates improved *Ulva*'s physicochemical stability, limiting the inactivation of the polyphenolic compounds, and achieving high encapsulation efficiency associated with good bioactive protection. The microencapsulates demonstrated good powder properties, parameters important for further applications. The thermal analysis proved *Ulva* microencapsulates have good thermal stability important for food processing. All fragments from this valuable sea resource may be used as uncostly bio-products rich in functional compounds, which could have commercial utilization and benefit *Ulva* species present along the Adriatic Sea.

This experimental research work has been performed by the frame of Cost Action 20106 (SeaWheat), supported by the grant for the STSM project, and experiments with *Ulva spp.* were performed at the Institute of Marine Biology, Kotor, Montenegro. Authors acknowledge the Cost Action 22161 (FLAVOURsome) and the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia, grant number 451-03-66/2024-03/200003.

Keywords: *Ulva*, extraction, microencapsulation, carriers, polyphenols

T8: Environmental education

Education of fishermen as a stakeholders tool in preserving biodiversity

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Abstract

Education of commercial and recreational fishermen is an important tool in sustaining autochthonous biodiversity. The challenge for the stakeholder is how to preserve the richness of species, habitats and have a sustainable fishing area. Education of recreational fishermen is a duty for stakeholders by the law. There is no obligation to participate in education, no exam or recreational fishing license. Minimum knowledge about sustainable fishing is not obligatory. Those activities produce an impact on fish stock. Responsibility is on stakeholder to educate and promote importance of protection and conservation of biodiversity, to preserve and improve heterogeneity of aquatic ecosystems and species throughout implementation of Fishery Management Plans. Besides being an economic activity commercial fishing is part of tradition, but not visible or recognized in terms of positioning and preservation. Commercial fishermen have an exam for gaining a license and a number in register, but no obligation to improve knowledge. Stakeholders may have joint education with fishing associations, clubs, scientific institutions, NGOs. Networking of institutions contributes to cooperation and speed up information. Stakeholders have websites, update all the data and education materials on the web, but not all fishermen have digital knowledge. Educational materials are distributed to fishermen when purchasing a permit. Educational informative boards contribute conservation of fish communities. When activity produces impact on biodiversity, there is a strong need to valorise and measure knowledge before you allow it. Exam for gaining a license for recreational fishing and license renewal for commercial fishing would help stakeholders to actively implement field protection measures.

Keywords: stakeholder, sustainable fishing, biodiversity education

Optimizing Benthic Marine Research through Advanced Photogrammetry Techniques

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Abstract

Traditional *in situ* transect methodologies for studying benthic marine species' populations, densities, and distributions are time-consuming and labor-intensive. These methods necessitate extensive underwater hours, posing significant health risks and financial burdens. This study introduces an innovative approach using advanced photogrammetry to significantly enhance data collection efficiency, reduce health hazards, and minimize costs. By generating detailed orthophotomosaics of the study areas, our method enables precise population estimations and density analyses from the safety of the laboratory. This technique not only streamlines the counting and calculation processes but also narrows the scale of estimations, thereby improving accuracy. Utilizing state-of-the-art underwater cameras and equipment, our methodology extends research capabilities to previously inaccessible depths, now made feasible and affordable. This advancement allows for the examination of both target and non-target species within benthic communities, yielding a comprehensive analysis. Furthermore, our approach democratizes scientific research by empowering citizen scientists and recreational divers with the use of affordable cameras, such as GoPro, to contribute valuable data. This not only further reduces the manpower requirements and associated risks but also capitalizes on the methodology's minimal learning curve for widespread adoption. Additionally, the potential for integrating recordings from remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) and underwater sleds with mounted cameras is explored, broadening the scope of data collection possibilities. In conclusion, the introduction of photogrammetry in benthic marine research marks a significant leap forward in the field, offering a more efficient, safe, and inclusive method for studying underwater ecosystems.

Keywords: photogrammetry, habitat mapping, marine conservation, non-invasive techniques, orthophotomosaics

Photogrammetric Analysis and Spatial Mapping of *Aplysina aerophoba*

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Abstract

Addressing the urgent need for innovative conservation strategies in the Adriatic Sea, this research utilizes photogrammetry to enhance the monitoring and protection of *Aplysina aerophoba*, a protected marine sponge species. Unlike traditional research methodologies that often disrupt fragile marine ecosystems, photogrammetry offers a minimally invasive alternative, extending its application from terrestrial to marine environments. This photogrammetric approach allowed for an unprecedented level of detail in mapping the distribution and documenting the morphological dynamics of *A. aerophoba*. The generated data facilitated a comprehensive analysis of growth patterns and structural changes, providing vital insights into the ecological dynamics within the sponge's habitat. By pinpointing areas of dense populations and regions where the species is under threat, the study delivered critical information for targeted conservation actions, enhancing efforts to preserve marine biodiversity in the region. The results underscore the value of photogrammetry in producing detailed, accurate representations of marine organisms, which are essential for ongoing conservation assessments and future ecological research. The method's non-invasive nature ensures that the integrity of delicate underwater ecosystems is maintained, setting a new standard for conducting marine biology research with minimal environmental impact.

Keywords: photogrammetry, *Aplysina aerophoba*, spatial mapping, 3d modeling, non-invasive techniques

Transforming waste into resource: A potential of *Posidonia oceanica* waste valorization for biocomposites

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Abstract

When the leaves of *Posidonia oceanica* (PO) decompose, they are carried to the coasts, forming large banks that serve as a natural barrier against sea erosion, providing protection to the beaches. The roots and rhizome fragments come together to form fibrous sea balls, known as egagropili, which are shaped and collected by the waves along the shoreline. Tourists often have a negative perception of their presence on the beach, which causes local governments to view them as waste to be removed and disposed of. In order to address the issue of marine waste it is crucial to explore innovative solutions. PO waste has the potential to be utilised as a valuable renewable substrate in various biotechnological processes. It has the potential to be used as bio-adsorbent for environmental decontamination, in the production of bioplastics and biocomposites, and as insulating and reinforcement material in construction and building. This paper provides an overview of the current advancements of utilizing PO waste as an environmentally friendly reinforcement material for composite materials. Known for its significant cellulose content, robust fibers, and natural biodegradability, PO shows great potential for reinforcing composites. The paper explores different processing techniques used to incorporate PO waste into composites. These techniques include mechanical treatments like shredding and milling, as well as potential chemical modifications to improve compatibility with various matrix materials such as bio-based polymers or resins. The paper analyzes the resulting biocomposite properties, focusing on mechanical performance and biodegradability. Furthermore, the paper addresses key challenges associated with utilizing PO waste for composites, such as pre-treatment requirements to remove impurities and improve fiber-matrix adhesion, potential variability in PO composition depending on location, and the need for cost-effective large-scale processing methods.

Keywords: *Posidonia oceanica*, marine waste, biocomposites

Thermoregulation in Hermann's tortoise in a changing thermal environment: A year long perspective

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Abstract

The importance of temperature in the lives of reptiles is well known and most species to reach optimum body temperatures must devote time basking in the sun to harness heat. This is especially important in temperate regions where heat levels fluctuate on a daily and seasonal basis thus impacting on basking opportunities. This is especially important in larger reptiles that must bask for longer periods compared to smaller species to attain optimum body temperatures. Hermann's tortoise is an example of one of the larger species that is found across southern Europe that thermoregulates primarily by shuttling between sunlit and shaded patches in an attempt to attain preferred body temperatures. The present study gives a unique insight into a complete season of thermoregulatory activity in a reptile and how it responds to seasonal changes in the thermal environment derived from data from a population in Montenegro. Three sources of information were employed; tortoise body temperatures, set point temperatures (defined as the preferred body temperatures) and the temperatures of null models (appropriately sized metal cylinders) that give information on the heat available in the environment. This enabled calculations of seasonal thermoregulatory efficiency and when the tortoises were either active or inactive in relation to environmental temperatures. Activity was first recorded in late March through the summer months with entry into winter dormancy in late October when temperatures declined. Body temperatures of males and females were in approximate agreement throughout the active year, despite size differences and faster heating rates in males. Efficiency of thermoregulation was highest during April in both males and females and high for most of the active year. Tortoises frequently allowed body temperatures to exceed the preferred or set point range during the hottest months. This enabled the continuation of foraging and other activities.

Keywords: Thermoregulation, Hermann's tortoise, Montenegro

Characteristics of aquarium Dubrovnik and Boka visits

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Abstract

This paper analyzes visitor characteristics at Aquarium Dubrovnik (Croatia) and Aquarium Boka (Montenegro) based on surveys conducted in October 2022. A total of 2,998 questionnaires were collected from visitors at both locations, focusing on socio-demographics, biodiversity knowledge, and engagement. The study found notable differences between the two aquaria. Aquarium Boka attracted mainly school groups and had higher visitor numbers, while Aquarium Dubrovnik had more individual visitors. The age distribution varied, with younger visitors at Boka and older ones at Dubrovnik. Educational levels also differed, with Dubrovnik visitors generally more educated. Knowledge of biodiversity was greater among Aquarium Boka visitors, with younger demographics showing better understanding. Awareness of endangered Adriatic species was inconsistent, with more accurate knowledge among younger visitors and gaps in understanding regarding some species. Perceptions of political responsibility for biodiversity protection varied, with Dubrovnik visitors expressing less confidence in governmental and EU roles compared to Boka visitors. Most respondents at both aquaria were first-time visitors, indicating potential for growth through promotions like season tickets. Engagement in environmental organizations was low, though environmental awareness was high among visitors. Interest in outdoor activities was notable, with a preference for water sports and diving, while interest in angling and sailing was lower. The findings suggest a need for improved educational programs, better information on endangered species, and promotional strategies to boost repeat visits. The low interest in participating in future research highlights the need for incentives to enhance data collection in subsequent studies.

Keywords: visitor characteristics, aquarium comparisons, biodiversity awareness, socio-demographic analysis, environmental engagement

Public understanding of Adriatic Sea biodiversity

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Abstract

This paper assesses public understanding of Adriatic Sea biodiversity and protective actions through an online survey conducted on Aquarium Boka's website in October 2022, with 54 responses collected. The survey focused on: biodiversity terminology, wildlife-related value orientations, perceptions of biodiversity change, knowledge of Adriatic species, views on political actors, aquarium visit expectations and experiences, engagement in environmental organizations, interest in outdoor activities, and follow-up. Socio-demographics showed a higher proportion of females and university-educated respondents compared to personal pooling. There was a balance between local residents and tourists, with most respondents living in cities. Biodiversity knowledge was strong, with respondents showing a good understanding of biodiversity's importance, particularly for tourism. Wildlife-related value orientations revealed significant concern about global and regional biodiversity changes, but less about local changes. Higher age and education levels were associated with greater concern. Knowledge of Adriatic species was mostly accurate, with respondents aware that sea turtles, dolphins, and seahorses are endangered. Misunderstandings persisted about sea bass and mussels. Views on political responsibility indicated that conservationists and industry were seen as highly responsible, while perceptions of the EU's role were slightly lower. Aquarium visit expectations showed that most respondents had visited Aquarium Boka 1-2 times, motivated by seeing animals and family time. The lack of season ticket holders suggests potential for growth. Aquarium visit experiences were positive, with respondents valuing the aquarium's role in biodiversity protection. Group visits and staff interactions were common, with increased use of the Blue Pass EXChAngE app. Engagement in environmental organizations was low, but environmental awareness was high. Interest in outdoor activities varied, with diving and swimming being most popular.

Keywords: Adriatic Sea biodiversity, aquarium visitor knowledge, environmental awareness, species conservation, public perceptions

T9: Elasmobranch biodiversity, conservation, and management

Collecting data on elasmobranchs in a developing country: achieved goals and experiences of Montenegro

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Abstract

Sharks, rays and chimaeras (hereinafter as chondrichthyans) are considered one of the most threatened vertebrate groups in the world nowadays. Severe declines in their populations were observed worldwide, primarily due to overfishing, and the Mediterranean Sea is often considered a region where the threat level is considerably high. Taking into account the negative beliefs and fears related to these species, often firmly established in communities, making the protection of this group effective is even more challenging. Montenegro belongs to developing countries, and thus providing resources for research and monitoring of such species is much more difficult than in the case of other, more economically important marine organisms. Efforts to improve available chondrichthyan-related scientific data in Montenegro have intensified over the past years, mostly relying on cost-effective citizen science data collection. This resulted in existence of citizen science dataset, with contemporary records of 27 chondrichthyans, of which many are considered rare or endangered. These data contributed to relevant regional initiatives, and were used to create the first chondrichthyan checklist of Montenegro and provide insight into the frequency of each species in the local catch.

Keywords: conservation, threatened species, chondrichthyans, Adriatic Sea, sharks

Critical life stage (recruits and spawners) and spatial analyses of 2 ray and 2 shark species in the Albanian territorial waters

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Abstract

Chondrichthyans represent a diverse group of cartilaginous fishes that includes sharks, skates, rays, and chimaeras. The conservation of Mediterranean chondrichthyans faces challenges not only from the fishery industry itself, but also from the significant unreliability of official catch data. The species in this group often occupy upper trophic levels, displaying K-selected life history traits characterized by slow growth, late maturity, low fecundity and long gestation periods. The Mediterranean Sea is known to be a chondrichthyan-rich area inhabited by 88 species, of which almost half are consistently recorded in the basin. The Adriatic Sea represents a sub-basin and falls within the northeastern part of the Mediterranean Sea. Based on the data collected in the frame of MEDITS survey programme (International bottom trawl survey in the Mediterranean) coordinated by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development with the support of General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM), through the 2023 bottom trawl surveys, we conducted the relative analysis for identifying the recruits and spawners abundance of Mediterranean starry ray (*Raja asterias*), brown ray (*Raja miraletus*), blackmouth catshark (*Galeus melastomus*) and lesser spotted dogfish (*Scyliorhinus canicula*). In addition we did some preliminary spatial analyses in order to identify the spatial hotspots of each considered species spawners and recruits in Albanian territorial waters. These are the first reported spatial analyses data so far and other analyses would be required to identify important shark and ray areas in the Adriatic Sea.

Keywords: Chondrichthyans, fisheries, Mediterranean Sea, Adriatic Sea, spatial analyses, critical life stage

Multidisciplinary approach to study the interaction and survival of pelagic sharks in recreational fishery in the Northern Adriatic Sea

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Abstract

Recreational fisheries in the Northern Adriatic Sea consist of a range of fishing techniques targeting several species. Drifting is one of the most commonly used methods, employed especially for catch and release fishing of Atlantic bluefin tuna (*Thunnus thynnus*). This fishery is also known to accidentally catch pelagic shark species, though the species catch composition, its seasonality, and potential impact on the shark assemblage in the region is poorly understood. In the last four years, logbook data were collected in collaboration with nearly 20 drifting fishers to assess the by-catch rate and area of occurrence of three neritic sharks. Among these species, the blue shark (*Prionace glauca*) is the most frequently caught, followed by the common thresher shark (*Alopias vulpinus*) and the sandbar shark (*Carcharhinus plumbeus*). Questionnaires were also used to gather local ecological knowledge (LEK) regarding the by-catch rate, area of seasonal occurrence, age composition, and post-release survival perception for the three species. Finally, post-release survival of these species is being assessed through the deployment of a combination of conventional (spaghetti tag), acoustic (sentinel array of 18 VR2tX receivers and V13 transmitters by Innovasea) and satellite (sPAT) tagging. This multidisciplinary approach has the potential to contribute to closing the knowledge gap on the movement ecology of these species in the Northern Adriatic Sea, while also helping to quantify the potential impact of drifting fishing on shark populations.

Keywords: recreational fishing, sharks, survival rate, local ecological knowledge, pelagic sharks

Using local ecological knowledge to understand the recreational fishing impact on elasmobranch populations in the Northern Adriatic Sea coastal area

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Abstract

Citizen science records and the local ecological knowledge (LEK) are powerful tools to provide a lot of useful information about the interaction between elasmobranchs and recreational fishing. In the Northern Adriatic Sea (Mediterranean Sea) recreational fisheries consist of a range of fishing techniques targeting several species and the impact of this activity on demersal elasmobranch species is still poorly known. The aim of this study is to investigate, through online questionnaires, the impact of recreational fishing on some elasmobranch species (e.g., *Mustelus* spp., *Squalus acanthias*, and batoids), in the North-East Adriatic coastal area. A total of 132 questionnaires were collected between December 2022 and October 2023. The data collected shows how the fishing effort seems to be higher near the port entrance of the Venice Lagoon. Regarding the shark catches, 77% of anglers reported catching *Mustelus* spp., 77% never have caught *S. acanthias*, and 41% reported regularly catching batoids. 83% of the anglers release sharks and rays after capture. The data collected highlight a higher catchability of the smooth-hounds, especially in the areas where the fishing effort is higher. The collaboration with recreational fishery could provide precious information on the negative effect of these activities on these species such as post release mortality and about the presence and abundance of demersal elasmobranch species in the Northern Adriatic Sea, especially in Venice Lagoon, where there is no possibility to obtain this data from commercial fishing activities.

Keywords: elasmobranchs, recreational fishing, local ecological knowledge

Elasmobranch research in the Adriatic Sea: experiences from Slovenia

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Abstract

The fate of elasmobranchs in the Adriatic Sea and the whole Mediterranean basin is unclear. Due to their vulnerability to fishing pressure they are facing an unprecedented and dramatic decimation in their numbers. Since they are apex predators they can regulate prey species densities and their distribution, they are considered as suitable indicators of environmental health, however, they are still poorly investigated. Authors wish to present the state of the art of elasmobranch research in the Adriatic Sea with experiences gained through research performed in its northernmost part and try to propose some options to improve the elasmobranch research and possible conservation measures. During the last decades certain elasmobranch species were regularly caught by fishermen as target species and many other as bycatch in local coastal fishery. Among them some rare and less known species were recorded, as well. Many interesting facts were discovered in the Slovenian waters and in the northern Adriatic, as well. Many neonate and juvenile specimens of sharks and batoids were recorded, which confirm the hypothesis that the study area may serve as a nursery for many elasmobranchs. Although the shallow waters of the Gulf of Trieste offer good opportunities to reproduce and for the development of young specimens, they also represent a threat for many species. During the last twenty years many cases of large sized shark entanglements in fishermen nets were recorded.

Keywords: sharks, rays, ecology, nursery, marine pollution, northern Adriatic, conservation

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